

ELIXIR Biodiversity,
Food Security and
Pathogens
2024-26
Work Plan v2

ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens 2024-2028 Work Plan

Abstract

In the priorities of the ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-2028, molecular science connecting biodiversity, food security and pathogens has been identified as a societal challenge and scientific opportunity set as a core domain that shapes ELIXIR's activities. The Programme stresses that the application of molecular techniques is critical to understand the diversity and breadth of life on Earth. In other words, the diversity of life, rapidly changing climate, increasing contact between the natural world and humans can influence emerging infectious agents which impact not only humans, but also farmed animals, crops and wildlife.

The Commissioned Service contributes to that Priority through the provision of leadership, community engagement, and open project calls:

- Leadership and Strategy: A team drives strategy, supported by the ELIXIR Hub.
- Community Engagement: ELIXIR Community Members are engaged via meetings and calls.
- Pilot studies and Open Calls: Members submit projects aligned with the roadmap.

This effort connects the ELIXIR Communities and Nodes in their response to advances in biodiversity, food security and pathogens and enables these advances to contribute to wider research questions.

About this document

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1. Objectives and relation to the Scientific Programme

ELIXIR's Programme 2024-2028 is organised around four Priorities, of which the first is a focus on science - to "enable scientists to access and analyse life science data". This priority outlines three Ambitions, of which the second is to "Mobilise and integrate life science data to support transnational research programmes in biodiversity, food security and pathogens", the technologies and data types which underpin all of ELIXIR's activities. As outlined in the ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-2028,

"The areas of biodiversity, food security and pathogens represent critical societal challenges that Europe must address over the next decade, and which are strongly enabled by the application of molecular sciences and other data-intense disciplines. The importance of these scientific areas in contributing to societal challenges is also widely recognised by major transnational and national funding bodies and is reflected in their research strategies."

To work towards this goal ELIXIR needs to understand the molecular techniques used in this area, establish a clear roadmap, identify key internal partners and nourish connections to external partners, e.g. other Research Infrastructures, and develop our presence in the national as well as international funding landscape.

To reach this goal this Commissioned Service will make three main contributions to ELIXIR:

- Leadership and strategy development
- Community engagement
- Open call projects and/or pilot studies for the Priority Area.

We aim to contribute to solutions in the area by starting with a coordinated effort across ELIXIR Nodes and beyond, enabling the following.

Leadership: An advisory team of three experts has been identified to drive this ambition together with ELIXIR Hub support. Concrete activities are described as an activity in WP1 "ELIXIR Strategy for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens".

Community engagement: It is key to involve the ELIXIR Community in this effort. Hence another activity in WP1 focuses on engaging with ELIXIR members, to gain a wide overview of the theme, incentivise community building and start establishing our network of experts related to biodiversity, food security and pathogens. To do so different approaches will be used: A theme kick-off, midterm and final meeting combined with regular interactions, e.g. through regular cross-theme video-conference calls. Outcomes of these activities, combined with the consolidated leadership activities will incentivise knowledge exchange and inform the writing of the ambition roadmap.

Pilot studies and/or Open Call Projects call for the community: Once the theme roadmap has been defined ELIXIR members are best placed to work towards identified aims. A third task in WP1 will be to work with the vast expertise of ELIXIR members and prepare Open Calls for projects to be submitted. ELIXIR members will hence contribute towards the identified roadmap, with a diverse range of projects of different sizes and breadth of scope. Collaborations across disciplines (e.g. involving several ELIXIR Communities) will be incentivised and rewarded.

The open call is expected to run during 2024 allowing for projects to start in 2025, and again in 2026 for projects in the later parts of the Programme. Selected pilot studies may be developed in advance or in parallel with the Open Call projects.

2. Partnership

Contributors to the work programme are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of involved institutions. Leads highlighted in **bold**.

Node	Institution	Abbreviation
CH	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (Lead)	CH-SIB
FR	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE) (Lead)	FR-INRAE
GR	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research HCMR (Lead)	GR-HCMR
ELIXIR	ELIXIR Hub	ELIXIR-HUB
BE	Flanders Institute for Biotechnology	BE-VIB
DE	University of Freiburg	DE-FREIBURG
DE	Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research	DE-IPK
DE	Research Center Jülich GmbH, Jülich	DE-FZJU
DE	Forschungszentrum für Gesundheit und Umwelt GmbH, München	DE-HMGU
EMBL	EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute	EMBL-EBI
ES	Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII)	ES-ISCIII
FR	CNRS - Institut français de bioinformatique (IFB)	FR-IFB-CNRS
FR	CNRS - CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	FR-CNRS
FR	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE/Emphasis.fr)	FR-INRAE
GR	Democritus University of Thrace	GR-DUTH
GR	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	GR-AUTH
GR	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	GR-CERTH
GR	Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH)	GR-FORTH
GR	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	GR-NKAU
IT	University of Bari	IT-UNIBA
IT	National Research Council	IT-CNR
IT	University of Naples "Federico II"	IT-UNINA
NL	Wageningen University & Research	NL-WUR

NL	Leiden University	NL-Leiden
NL	Utrecht University	NL-ULTRECHT
NL	Delft University of Technology	NL-DELFT
NO	Norwegian University of Life Sciences	NO-NMBU
NO	The Arctic University of Norway	NO-UiT
PT	NOVA University of Lisbon (Institute of Chemical and Biological Technology)	PT-ITQB NOVA
PT	BIP4DAB Association (BioData)	PT-BioData
SI	National Institute of Biology (NIB)	SI-NIB
UK	Rothamsted Research	UK-ROTHAMSTE D
UK	University of Oxford (Oxford e-Research Center)	UK-UNIOXF
UK	University of Manchester	UK-UNIMAN
UK	Quadram Institute Bioscience	UK-QIB
Total		

*Institution not receiving any funding in CoS

3. Work Package descriptions

Work Package 1 - ELIXIR Strategy for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens

	CH-SIB - Rob Waterhouse (Lead)
	FR-INRAE - Cyril Pommier (Lead)
	GR-HCMR, Tereza Manousaki (Lead)
	ELIXIR-HUB - Katharina Heil (Coordinator), Physilia Chua
	Total

Objectives

- Develop and document background understanding of the developments in Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research which will impact the application of molecular techniques.
- Write a Strategy to guide ELIXIR's priorities and decision making when participating in activities in support of Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research.
- Develop a Roadmap for ELIXIR direct investments and participation in projects and consortia in this area.
- Engage with ELIXIR Communities and gather their requirements and proposed contributions to the Roadmap.
- Build active working relationships with partner Research Infrastructures and international consortia.
- Guide the selection and development of new ELIXIR Communities relevant to Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens.
- Through pilot studies, demonstrate ways of working across the Communities connected to the theme.
- Through open calls, leverage the ELIXIR network to develop approaches and technologies to solve problems of pan-European working.
- Update the Work Plan for the next period, 2027-2028.

Description of work

This work package will allow the leadership team to coordinate a programme of work across the theme, through three activities - strategy development, community engagement, and running pilots & open calls and/or pilot studies.

Members from all Nodes are invited to contribute to the shaping of the scientific theme/ambition. They will get together regularly to develop a roadmap and later on become participants and applicants in the open project call. Wide engagement is necessary to consider distinct national roadmaps, activities ongoing in active projects and to bring together knowledge and coordinate ongoing activities linked to the Theme across Europe and the world. A core activity will be to scope ELIXIR's possible contribution to the area, with regards to molecular techniques and data (management, stewardship, ...) without directly competing with spaces already covered by others, e.g. other Research Infrastructures.

Activity 1: ELIXIR Strategy for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research (*Leads: Rob Waterhouse (CH), Cyril Pommier (FR), Tereza Manousaki (GR); Members: Katharina Heil (ELIXIR-HUB), Physilia Chua (ELIXIR-HUB). M1-M36.*)

Working in partnership with Hub staff, Hub Management Team, ELIXIR Heads of Nodes and ELIXIR Scientific Advisory Board, the co-leads of the theme will develop a Strategy connecting the ELIXIR Services, Platforms, Communities and Projects to ensure effective coordination of efforts for the benefit of research scientists working within the basic science areas of biodiversity, food security and pathogens and for those who depend on these technologies for translational, environmental, societal or industrial impact.

This work will involve being available for regular meetings with ELIXIR Members (for example the monthly Programme TC and the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting) and in support of ELIXIR outreach to partner Research Infrastructures and international partners, in addition to regular meetings of participants in this Commissioned Service funded through Pilot Studies or Open Calls and/or Pilot Studies.

The co-leads and Hub will develop a Strategy and a multi-annual Roadmap for investments, updated annually, and will consult widely to develop a renewed Work Plan for 2027-2028 and input into the 2029+ Programme.

Activity 2: Engagement with the ELIXIR Communities (*Leads: Rob Waterhouse (CH), Cyril Pommier (FR), Tereza Manousaki (GR); Members: Katharina Heil (ELIXIR-HUB), Physilia Chua (ELIXIR-HUB). M1-M36.*)

ELIXIR's engagement in Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research will be primarily facilitated by the ELIXIR Communities working in this area. The theme co-leads will meet regularly to engage in dialogue with the Community co-leads and Community

membership, promote and support their individual activities, and discuss the Open Calls and other funding opportunities.

Direct Community engagement and input into the Strategy and Roadmap will be enabled by face to face cross-community workshops organised throughout the project. Two face to face workshops will be organised (approximately 25 people each). The Hub will support the organisation of these workshops, while the co-leads will guide the content, the topics covered, invitations to external partners, and reporting of outcomes.

With regards to Communication and Dissemination this activity hence relies on the members to advocate for the theme, use their existing connections to bring knowledge to this forum and enable the best possible understanding of the landscape.

Activity 3: Open calls for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research
(Leads: Rob Waterhouse (CH), Cyril Pommier (FR), Tereza Manousaki (GR); Members: Katharina Heil (ELIXIR-HUB), Physilia Chua (ELIXIR-HUB). M5-M36).

The main focus of the funded effort for the theme will be Work Packages funded through an Open Call process. The co-leads and Hub will draft call text, write review criteria, and run Open Calls - one during 2024 for projects to be implemented in 2025-2026, one during 2026 for projects to be funded during the next period 2027-2028.

These calls will be the opportunity for ELIXIR Communities to take a lead on the development of new data management or analysis capabilities, integration of existing resources to meet particular cross-domain challenges, or the investigation of the impact new classes of computational technology or new experimental data types on ELIXIR's Services and Membership. Successful projects may combine multiple ELIXIR Communities and ELIXIR Services and align them with the developments of the ELIXIR Platforms and partner externally-funded projects.

The Hub and co-leads will provide an initial review of the quality and impact of the projects funded through the Open Calls, and summarise their contribution in the final Report.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D1.1	Report and Roadmap on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens in ELIXIR 2024-2025	CH-SIB	M13
D1.2	Report and Roadmap on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens in ELIXIR 2025-2026	FR-INRAE	M25
D1.3	Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research 2027-2028 Work Plan	GR-HCMR	M30
D1.4	Final Report 2024-2026	CH-SIB	M36

Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M1.1	2024 Open Call for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	FR-INRAE	M03
M1.2	Cross-Community workshop on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	CH-SIB	M09
M1.3	2026 Open Call for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	GR-HCMR	M27
M1.4	Cross-Community workshop on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	GR-HCMR	M33

Work Package 2 - E-PAN: Enhancing pan-genome analysis in plants

WP 2	Lead Partner: BE-VIB
	Start month - End month: M13-29
WP Partnership	
BE-VIB, Klaas Vandepoele Lead (WP and Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
DE-FZJU, Sebastian Beier, Lead (Activity 1)	
UK-ROTHAMSTED, Keywan Hassani-Pak Lead (Activity 3) , Member (Activity 4)	
DE-IPK, Uwe Scholz Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2)	
PT-ITQB NOVA, M. Margarida Oliveira, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 4)	
SI-NIB, Kristina Gruden, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 4)	
DE-HMGU, Heidrun Gundlach Member (Activity 1)	
Total	

Objectives

The adaptive differences between genotypes of the same species can only be explained by exploring genomic diversity through pan-genomics. The sequencing and assembly of pan-genomes no longer pose significant scientific challenges, but the subsequent data integration and exploration is hampered by a lack of standards and tools. For example, a simple comparison of the sequences of 44 potato genomes (Tang et al., Nature 2020) would not lead to any significant insights. However, the investigation of gene Presence Absence Variation (PAV) and structural rearrangements highlighted loci of interest to link intra-species genotypic with phenotypic diversity.

The global objective of the E-PAN project is to accelerate the use of pan-genome data through advances in data quality control, curation, integration, and visualisation. These objectives can be placed on different axes, which can be progressed in parallel:

- Methods for ensuring high-quality pan-genome data. In order to ascertain that PAVs are biological and not technical artefacts, the need for quality control (QC) and standardisation is clear. Solely using BUSCO (Seppey et al., Methods Mol Biol 2019) for estimating genome and gene space completeness of pan-genomes will miss nearly all intra-species differentiation. Therefore new standards and methodologies, benchmarked against real data from a broad phylogenetic species selection, are required. This will result in new guidelines and tutorials for pan-genome QC.

- Computation and standardised reporting of gene-based PAVs and structural variants. Apart from implementing efficient and scalable algorithms to quantify different types of structural variants, the obtained results will be shared in a standardised manner between the different plant resources, resulting in better access to pan-genomics results for diverse plant species.
- Visualisation and integration of pan-genomes and derived results. Current approaches to visualising pan-genomes do not automatically lead to easily-interpretable results using the current set of data integration tools. Therefore, we aim to evaluate and prototype a set of visualisation modules that can be (re)used in multiple plant databases. These will connect complementary resources and enhance the extraction of biological knowledge for key agricultural species.

Based on the expertise of all partners involved and the numerous interactions with different stakeholders involved in data generation, tool development, as well as biological interpretation of plant genome information, we will address these objectives in four Activities:

Activity 1. Development and evaluation of standards for quality control and sharing of plant pan-genomes;

Activity 2. Improvement of algorithms to characterise pan-genome dynamics and data visualisation;

Activity 3. Connecting and sharing pan-genome information across different plant platforms;

Activity 4. Community building to foster interactions between (ELIXIR) plant genome platforms.

These Activities align with the overall activities of the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community, especially on the aspect of developing community resources (PLAZA) and enabling future opportunities for wider integration. New guidelines for the creation of pan-genome resources and the workshop will also address training aspects, which are a central theme of ELIXIR. Building on E-PAN's experience and best practices, this will create new tools and web resources that will simplify and standardise the handling of pan-genome data.

Description of work

Within the E-PAN project we aim to enhance pan-genome data analysis by focusing on data quality control, curation, integration, and visualisation. While a lot of work has been done on representing species' genetic diversity during/after assembly, for example by constructing complex genome graphs, most biologists have a strong interest in understanding how this intra-species diversity affects the presence/absence of specific

genes and their associated functions. However, publicly available tools and data standards helping to address these questions are scarce. Consequently, this project primarily focuses on the gene-based comparative analysis of plant pan-genomes. By employing specific data visualisations (e.g., Activity 2), we also seek to establish links between gene PAV and the corresponding genomic DNA sequences. By focusing on a selection of species of major importance for agriculture and plant research (barley, potato, wheat, rice and the model *Arabidopsis*), the project will have both a societal and industry impact, narrowing the divide between research institutions and the crop breeding companies.

Activity 1: Development and evaluation of standards for quality control and sharing of plant pan-genomes (3.5 PMs) (*Leads: Sebastian Beier (DE); Members: Klaas Vandepoele (BE), Heidrun Gundlach (DE), Uwe Scholz (DE), M. Margarida Oliveira (PT), Kristina Gruden (SI), Keywan Hassani-Pak (UK). M13-M19).*

ELIXIR Germany will take the lead in developing the necessary standards and tools to evaluate and assess the quality of pan-genomes. ELIXIR Belgium will provide the necessary expertise for tool development and integration of the tools in existing workflows (e.g., NextFlow).

Pan-genome data exchange standardisation and development will be a shared responsibility of ELIXIR Germany, Belgium, and UK. ELIXIR Slovenia and Portugal will deliver pan-genomes, perform the necessary tests and feedback, and draft tutorials. Facilitating data exchange, and how to make the data FAIR, is one of the key selling points of the project, and as such will require the combined effort of all partners. By iteratively improving the proposed solutions, and testing them out using real data, we hope to come to a common standard that all parties can consent to.

Tasks:

T1.1: Data quality control standardisation (M1-M3);

T1.2: Data quality control implementation (M3-M6);

T1.3: Data exchange standardisation and development (M3-M4).

Activity 2: Improvement of algorithms to characterise pan-genome dynamics and data visualisation (2.25 PMs) (*Leads: Klaas Vandepoele (BE); Members: Uwe Scholz (DE). M16-M20).*

ELIXIR Belgium will be the leading partner in the additional development of tools and algorithms for the characterization of pan-genome dynamics at the gene level. These developments will be stand-alone based on shared data exchange principles as developed within Activity 1, but will also be integrated within existing data platforms (i.e. FRINGE, <https://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/plaza.dev/fringe> and the extension of

PanBARLEX, <https://panbarlex.ipk-gatersleben.de/> to a general tool for more species/crops).

Furthermore, prototyping different pan-genome visualisations (e.g., Panache [Tang et al., *Bioinformatics* 2021], SyRI-Barley as an interactive web tool for SyRI results [Goel et al., *Genome Biology* 2019]) and associated data protocols will be a shared development of ELIXIR Belgium and Germany.

Tasks:

T2.1: Tool development PAV detection (M5-M6);

T2.2: Tool development data visualisation(s) (M6-M7).

Activity 3: Connecting and sharing pan-genome information across different plant platforms (1.25 PMs) (*Leads: Keywan Hassani-Pak (UK); Members: Klaas Vandepoele (BE). M19-M22).*

ELIXIR UK, assisted by ELIXIR Belgium, will be the leading partner for the prototyping of data formats to exchange general pan-genome analysis results and integrate these in different platforms (e.g., PLAZA/FRINGE, KnetMiner). ELIXIR UK will also integrate new pan-genome information in KnetMiner knowledge graphs.

Tasks:

T3.1: Integration pan-genome information in PLAZA/FRINGE and KnetMiner (M8-M9).

Activity 4: Community building to foster interactions between (ELIXIR) plant genome platforms (1.25 PMs) (*Leads: Klaas Vandepoele (BE); Members: M. Margarida Oliveira (PT), Kristina Gruden (SI). M22-M25).*

A one-day event will be organised (by ELIXIR Belgium) where the results of this project and new opportunities for collaborative research will be discussed. We will invite both ELIXIR as well as external stakeholders to get a broad representation of plant genome experts. Based on the preparatory meetings in drafting this proposal, it became clear there is a lot of critical mass and momentum in the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community to boost plant pan-genome research and address key challenges. In addition, an online workshop will be organised to showcase the developed tools and practical use cases and exchange training material (ELIXIR Slovenia). Taken together, the E-PAN project combines the effective knowledge and data resources of multiple and complementary research groups within the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community and will give a strong boost to pan-genomics in the international plant research community. While the project focuses on a selection of crop and model species as a starting point, the acquired know-how on pan-genome analysis and standards can subsequently be used for projects within the bio-conservation and biodiversity research communities, where

genome sequencing is generating new resources with unprecedented scope and coverage (e.g., Earth BioGenome project, Darwin Tree of Life project).

Tasks:

T4.1: Organising of plant pan-genome meeting and online workshop (M10-M12)

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D2.1 (Activity 1)	Develop standards for assessment of pan-genome completeness	DE-FZJU	M16
D2.2 (Activity 2)	Computational pipelines to assess pan-genome data quality and characterise gene-based structural variation within pan-genomes	BE-VIB	M19
D2.3 (Activity 2)	Prototyping and evaluation of data visualisations to represent pan-genome dynamics	DE-IPK	M20
D2.4 (Activity 3)	Development of API calls and sharing of bulk-downloads to exchange pan-genome information across different platforms (PLAZA/FRINGE and KnetMiner) for the selected plant species	UK-Rothamsted	M22
D2.5 (Activity 4)	Training materials based on crop-specific use cases deposited at TeSS	PT-ITQB NOVA	M25
D2.6 (Activity 4)	Online workshop to showcase the developed tools and practical use cases	SI-NIB	M25

Outcomes and impact

We use the term “outcomes” and “impacts” as defined by the ELIXIR community, based on their respective spheres of influence and interest. Whereas “deliverables” are within the sphere of control of the project, “outcomes” cover effects outside the direct control of the ELIXIR partners, and “impacts” cover structural changes in the economy and society.

We envision multiple positive outcomes of this project on the research community in general, and the genome assembly/annotation community specifically. By adopting the standards and following the guidelines that we propose, future pan-genome projects will have overall higher quality and accuracy. Pan-genome QC metrics are currently quasi non-existent, leading to researchers independently trying to create new standards. Thus, by homogenising the QC, and eliminating redundant work, we also expect an impact on the field of genome research: faster QC, fewer issues during publication review, and standardised output. These new standards and guidelines will

also further streamline the processes of pan-genome data submission and integration in ELIXIR Core Data Resources such as ENA and Ensembl Genomes. All together the impact will result in significant savings in terms of both time and money.

We are expecting constructive feedback from researchers. It is to be expected that within our QC proposal, there will be inaccuracies or missing options for specific needs. Therefore having an open discussion with the community at large (WP4) will be of strategic interest for long-term support of the standards. Thus, we hope that E-PAN might kick-start the creation of a global community of researchers that can update the standards as needed. Such communities already exist, for example for plant phenotyping (EMPHASIS) and orthology (QuestForOrthologs). Consequently, ELIXIR can take up a leading position in this regard, and promote the adoption of these QC guidelines. Multiple other ELIXIR Communities, which may lack the expertise of the groups within this research proposal, may also benefit from this. For example, the guidelines can be implemented within Galaxy as a new workflow, the Biodiversity Community may employ the QC guidelines when sequencing new genomes, etc. Furthermore, publishing these guidelines under the banner of ELIXIR will enhance the visibility of both the ELIXIR organisation itself, as well as the data standards that ELIXIR develops and promotes.

We expect that the integration of new pan-genome data types in flagship ELIXIR platforms such as PLAZA, a RIR, and KnetMiner, will result in additional interest and an increasing number of new users from academia as well as industry. Thus, the implementation of new approaches and algorithms to evaluate and analyse pan-genomes, and new ways to visualise the data, might result in additional industrial income further down the line for these Node services.

The final impact of the project will be years downstream when breeding companies use the progress made in this project to enhance the quality of their in-house sequenced pan-genomes, and standardise their workflows around a global set of guidelines. This in turn should lead to optimizations of genome data mining, and improved crop selection and breeding techniques.

Work Package 3 - FAIRyMAGs - Optimising Metagenomics Assembled Genomes building: workflow finalisation, training material development, real data evaluation and resource allocation tool creation

WP 3	Lead Partner: DE-FREIBURG
	Start month - End month: M13-M30
WP Partnership	
DE-FREIBURG Paul Zierep, Lead (WP and Activity 1 and Activity 3) , Member (Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
FR-IFB Bérénice Batut, Lead (Activity 2 and Activity 4) , Member (Activity 1 and Activity 3)	
IT-UOB - Giuseppe Defazio, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 4), Bruno Fosso, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 4)	
IT-UNIBA - (Activity 4)	
EMBL-EBI, Martin Beracochea, Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4), Santiago Sanchez, Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
Total	

Objectives

The proposed project aligns closely with the objectives and priorities outlined in the ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security & Pathogens Scientific Priority Area, as articulated in the ELIXIR 2024-2028 Scientific Programme. This priority area within ELIXIR aims to mobilise and integrate genetics and omics data to support research programs in biodiversity, food security, and pathogens, including agriculture and aquaculture research.

The proposed project directly addresses these challenges by advancing metagenomics research, a field that plays a pivotal role in understanding and mitigating the impacts of biodiversity loss, enhancing food security, and combating pathogens in agricultural and environmental contexts. This project will be the first to offer a high-computation end-to-end MAGs workflow through Galaxy, incorporating FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles to benefit the research community.

The project's objectives are designed to contribute to the overarching goals of the ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security & Pathogens Scientific Priority Area:

- Metagenomics Building Workflow Design, Implementation, and Evaluation: To date, researchers face challenges in independently analysing

Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs) due to technically demanding workflows and high computational requirements. These issues will be addressed by implementing the workflows in Galaxy, a platform that facilitates easier execution and management of bioinformatics analyses, coupled with the computing resources of public servers. By finalising a Galaxy workflow for building MAGs, the project will empower researchers to investigate uncultured genomes with respect to biodiversity monitoring, pathogen detection, and agricultural research. This workflow will facilitate the analysis of microbial communities in diverse ecosystems, providing insights into biodiversity dynamics and pathogen prevalence. Through the evaluation of MAGs generated by the workflow using simulated and real-world data from diverse environments (atmosphere, marine, and cow gut microbiomes), the project will provide valuable insights into the performance and applicability of metagenomics approaches across different research domains and enable the adaptation of the workflows and its parameters to specific and potentially unexplored environments.

- **Accessibility and Reusability:** The integration of the developed workflow with WorkflowHub will ensure its accessibility, reusability, and extension by the broader research community. This aligns with ELIXIR's goal of fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing within the life sciences community, enabling researchers to leverage existing tools and resources to address pressing societal challenges. Galaxy workflows can be reused and adapted by using specific tools (and tool versions), databases, and workflow logic using a graphical workflow builder. To the best of our knowledge, this simplicity is unmatched by current MAGs workflows.
- **Training and Education:** The creation of FAIR educational materials hosted on the Galaxy Training Network and their delivery via a hybrid workshop will support capacity building and skills development in metagenomics analysis. It will equip researchers with the necessary expertise to utilise the workflow effectively and contribute to building a skilled workforce capable of harnessing molecular sciences for building new genomes. The generated training will help researchers to understand the workflows in detail and hence also allow for additional contributions to further development.
- **Resource Allocation:** The investigation of computational resource requirements for executing the workflow on various input datasets addresses the practical challenges associated with scaling metagenomics analysis. By developing a tool for estimating and allocating resources based on input data characteristics (such as kmer counts), the project will support efficient and cost-effective MAG

construction (also for non-Galaxy based workflows), facilitating broader adoption of metagenomics approaches in research and decision-making processes related to data management. The proposed tool could be extended to other resource-intensive computations, significantly decreasing the environmental impact of large parallelized workflows.

In summary, the proposed project exemplifies a concerted effort to harness molecular sciences and data-intensive approaches to address critical societal challenges related to biodiversity conservation, food security, and pathogen management. By aligning with the goals and priorities of the ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security & Pathogens Scientific Priority Area, the project will contribute to advancing scientific knowledge and supporting evidence-based decision-making in these vital domains.

Description of work

Activity 1: Workflow Design, Implementation, and Evaluation (3.5 PMs) (*Leads: Paul Zierep (DE); Members: Bérénice Batut (FR), Giuseppe Defazio (IT), Bruno Fosso*). M13-M30).

Activity 1 aims to refine, optimise, FAIRify, and evaluate the Galaxy-based workflow prototype for constructing Metagenomics Assembled Genomes (MAGs). Taxonomy classification and genome annotation will be integrated. The workflow parameters will be optimised for improved efficiency, accuracy, and scalability. To ensure the accessibility and reusability of the developed workflow, documentation, metadata, and test data will be prepared following FAIR principles. Through submission to the Intergalactic Workflow Commission (IWC) and WorkflowHub, the workflow will be made discoverable and interoperable, with continuous updates and maintenance to reflect enhancements and feedback. Validation will be conducted using the CAMI benchmarking infrastructure to ensure the workflow's robust performance against established standards. Therefore the CAMI infrastructure will also be integrated into Galaxy, facilitating FAIR benchmark methodology, for the community. To assess the performance of the developed workflow, 3 real-world metagenomics datasets from various environments will be gathered. The workflow will be used on those datasets to generate Metagenomics Assembled Genomes (MAGs) which will then be evaluated in collaboration with domain experts to ensure their accuracy and relevance.

Tasks:

T1.1: Refine the Galaxy-based workflow prototype for building Metagenomics Assembled Genomes (MAGs), integrate taxonomy classification and genome annotation of MAGs in the workflow, and optimise workflow parameters and configurations to enhance efficiency, accuracy, and scalability (M13 - M18);

T1.2: Prepare documentation, metadata, and test data following IWC and WorkflowHub guidelines, submit the developed workflow IWC and WorkflowHub, ensuring compliance with FAIR data principles for discoverability and interoperability, and continuously update and maintain the workflow on IWC and WorkflowHub to reflect improvements and address user feedback (M19 - M30);

T1.3: Validate the workflow using CAMI benchmarking infrastructure (datasets, tools) (M21 - M22);

T1.4: Gather real-world metagenomics datasets from diverse environments (atmosphere, marine, and cow gut microbiomes), execute the developed workflow on the collected datasets to generate Metagenomics Assembled Genomes (MAGs), and evaluate the generated MAGs with experts from the domain (M21 - M27).

Activity 2: Training Material Development and Delivery (2.0 PMs) (*Leads: Bérénice Batut (FR); Members: Paul Zierep (DE). M16-M30.*)

Activity 2 aims to empower researchers with the skills necessary for effective utilisation of the developed workflow by creating comprehensive training materials tailored to diverse expertise levels. Collaboration with experts from the ELIXIR Microbiome and Galaxy Communities will ensure the accuracy, relevance, and accessibility of these materials. They will be available through the Galaxy Training Network, findable on ELIXIR TeSS, and taught during one online workshop, that will be broadly advertised within the ELIXIR Communities and related European projects, to reach a global audience.

Tasks:

T2.1: Develop a tutorial tailored for researchers with varying levels of expertise (M16-M20);

T2.2: Collaborate with experts from the ELIXIR Microbiome and Galaxy Community to ensure the accuracy, relevance, and accessibility of training materials (M20-M24);

T2.3: Publish training materials on the Galaxy Training Network, making them freely accessible to the global research community (M25-M25);

T2.4: Organise and conduct one online workshop using the developed training material (M26-M30).

Activity 3: Computational Resource Allocation Tool Development (4.5 PMs) (*Leads: Paul Zierep (DE); Members: Bérénice Batut (FR), Martin Beracochea (EMBL-EBI), Santiago Sanchez (EMBL-EBI). M14-M28.*)

Activity 3 aims to streamline the computational resource allocation process for metagenomic assemblies by analysing input data characteristics and developing a machine-learning model to predict resource requirements. EMBL-EBI will provide extensive information about compute requirements for assemblies generated using the

MGNify pipeline. The implementation of a user-friendly tool based on this model together with rules assigned via the Galaxy Total Perspective Vortex (TPV) - a framework that allows the assignment of dynamic rules for Galaxy job execution - will enable to accurately estimate and allocate computational resources for executing the workflow on diverse datasets. The upper boundary of the resources available for the MAGs workflow is given by the European Galaxy instance, which currently provides 8 nodes with 1TB RAM and 36 cores and 1 node with 2TB RAM and 60 cores.

Tasks:

T3.1: Analyse the needed computational resources for metagenomics assembly using data provided by the MGNify platform and k-mer profiles of the input data (M14-M18)

T3.2: Build a Machine-learning model to predict the needed computational resources for the assembly based on the k-mer profile (M19-M22)

T3.3: Implement a tool for using this model to predict computational resources required for executing the workflow on different input datasets (M23-M27)

T3.4: Integrate the resource allocation tool and rules for resource allocation in Galaxy using Galaxy Total Perspective Vortex (TPV) (M27-M28)

Activity 4: Engagement & Dissemination (2.0 PMs) (*Leads: Bérénice Batut (FR); Members: Paul Zierp (DE), Giuseppe Defazio, Bruno Fosso (IT), (Martin Beracochea, Santiago Sanchez (EMBL-EBI). M15-M30).*

Activity 4 focuses on coordination and dissemination of the project. We will organise a hackathon in Freiburg (Germany) to discuss workflow demands, benchmarking procedures and the implementation of the resource allocation tool. This event will include all consortium partners and will also openly invite members from ELIXIR communities and European projects (e.g. NFDI4Microbiota, PHENET). The project outcomes will be communicated to the scientific community by writing a manuscript for peer-reviewed publication and submitting contributions to relevant scientific conferences for presentation. This will ensure that the developed workflow, resource allocation tool, and training materials reach a wide audience, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange in the field of metagenomics research.

Tasks:

T4.1: Organise and conduct hackathon in Freiburg (M15-M22);

T4.2: Write a manuscript for a peer-reviewed journal (M15-M30);

T4.3: Submit to present the work at a relevant scientific conference (M28-M30).

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D3.1 (Activity 1)	Workflow available on UseGalaxy Europe and UseGalaxy France servers as well as published on IWC and WorkflowHub.	DE-FREIBURG	M20
D3.2 (Activity 1)	Assessed MAGs and their quality for the 3 selected real-world datasets	DE-FREIBURG	M27
D3.3 (Activity 2)	Tutorial hosted on the Galaxy Training Network and visible on ELIXIR' TeSS	FR-IFB	M25
D3.4 (Activity 3)	Machine-Learning model registered on DOME registry and implemented to predict needed computational resources of metagenomic assembly tools for given input data and rules integrated into Galaxy Total Perspective Vortex (TPV)	DE-FREIBURG	M28
D3.5 (Activity 4)	Blogpost summarising the hackathon outcomes	DE-FREIBURG	M22
D3.6 (Activity 4)	Abstract for a talk at a conference submitted	FR-IFB	M30
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M3.1 (Activity 1)	Prototype and metadata of Galaxy workflow	DE-FREIBURG	M20
M3.2 (Activity 1)	Recovered MAGs for selection of 3 real-world datasets.	DE-FREIBURG	M24
M3.3 (Activity 2)	Online workshop	FR-IFB	M30
M3.4 (Activity 3)	Data from MGnify with computational resources used for metagenomics assembly	DE-FREIBURG	M18
M3.5 (Activity 4)	Hackathon in Freiburg	DE-FREIBURG	M22
M3.6 (Activity 4)	Preprint submitted on BioRxiv	FR-IFB	M30

Outcomes and impact

The proposed project is expected to yield significant outcomes and impact across multiple dimensions, including scientific advancement, capacity building, and societal benefit. At the core of these outcomes is the development and dissemination of a

robust metagenomics workflow tailored for building Metagenomics Assembled Genomes (MAGs) using the Galaxy platform, alongside associated training materials and computational resource optimization. These outcomes will contribute to the overarching goal of leveraging molecular sciences and data-intensive approaches to address pressing challenges in biodiversity, food security, and pathogen management.

1. Scientific Advancement:

- a. The finalisation of the Galaxy workflow for MAGs building will represent a significant advancement in metagenomics research, providing researchers with a standardised, FAIR, and user-friendly tool for analysing complex microbial communities.
- b. By conducting rigorous evaluations of MAGs generated by the workflow using real-world datasets, the project will enhance our understanding of microbial diversity, pathogen dynamics, and ecological processes across diverse environments. The envisioned MAGs benchmark framework will combine the MAGs workflow with benchmarking capability, allowing for a continuous benchmark of updated workflow versions, adapted to various sequencing and sample conditions.
- c. The project's focus on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data analysis using Galaxy ensures that research outputs are readily discoverable, accessible, and reusable, fostering transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration within the scientific community.

2. Capacity Building:

- a. The creation of FAIR training materials hosted on the Galaxy Training Network will empower researchers with the skills and knowledge necessary to effectively utilise the developed workflow for metagenomics analysis.
- b. An online workshop conducted as part of the project will further enhance capacity-building efforts, enabling researchers to leverage molecular data for biodiversity monitoring, agricultural research, and pathogen surveillance.

3. Societal Benefit:

- a. The availability of a production-ready metagenomics workflow and associated resources will enable researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding biodiversity conservation, food security enhancement, and pathogen management.
- b. By facilitating the analysis of microbial communities in agricultural and environmental contexts, the project supports efforts to enhance crop

productivity, mitigate disease outbreaks, and promote sustainable land management practices.

Work Package 4 - HARVEST: Handling and alignment of plant research FAIRification – value through the use of ELIXIR data Standards and Tools

WP 4	Lead Partner: DE-FZJU
	Start month - End month: M13-M30
WP Partnership	
DE-FZJU, Sebastian Beier, Lead (WP, Activity 4) , Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2)	
FR-INRAE, Cyril Pommier, Lead (Activity 3) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
DE-IPK, Daniel Arend, Lead (Activity 1) , Member (Activity 2, Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
EMBL-EBI, Timothee Cezard, Lead (Activity 2) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
UK-UNIOXF, Philippe Rocca-Serra, Member (Activity 2)	
NL-WUR, Matthijs Brouwer, Member (Activity 1)	
FR-INRAE (Emphasis.fr), Isabelle Alic, Member (Activity 1, Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
Total	

Objectives

We aim to improve existing resources with established data standards (MIAPPE, ISA, ARC, RO-Crate) to enhance plant data access and reusability over a project duration of 12 months. This will be done by (i) producing exemplar datasets using RO-Crate and MIAPPE, (ii) documenting this work to ease further adoption and outreach among biologists and computer scientists, and (iii) integrate those reference datasets in existing data repositories and services (FAIDARE data portal). This work will rely on the extension and connection of existing ELIXIR resources and services: RO-Crate data exchange package (<https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053>), the MIAPPE plant phenomics data standard (www.miappe.org), the RDMKit and FAIR Cookbook and the FAIDARE plant data portal. Most of those are registered in the Service Delivery Plans of national Nodes. We will also take advantage of established data repositories such as e!DAL-PGP, Zenodo and Dataverse (Recherche Data Gouv).

We will further develop several existing resources of the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community. Initially, we will extend and FAIRify at least two existing datasets from the DROPS and AGENT European projects, selected for their availability for public reuse, richness and representativeness of phenotypic and geospatial data for two major crop species: maize and wheat. The project outcome will facilitate the reuse of this data, but above all serve as example and documentation of machine actionable data sharing

using RO-Crate and MIAPPE. They will therefore be listed in the documentation of the standards as reference datasets and thus contribute to its adoption. Secondly, we will extend the plant related documentation on the RDMKit. Finally, we will expand the capabilities of FAIDARE and increase the number of indexed datasets.

We will connect technical resources (RO-Crate and MIAPPE) as well as data services and repositories (FAIDARE, e!DAL-PGP, Dataverse, Zenodo) used for crop data. For this we will rely on results produced within previous BioHackathons (<https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/7y2jh>) and Implementation Studies (FONDUE, Increasing).

We will improve the existing guidelines available on the RDMKit and FAIR Cookbook and enable outreach and adoption through webinars.

This project is well aligned with the past and future activities of the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community, in particular in terms of findability, sustainable access and reuse of data, the development of community recommendations and building of cross domain data linking and integration in particular between phenomics and other omics data. The latter, developed in collaboration with the European EMPHASIS infrastructure for plant phenotyping, relies on the sharing of common data resources identifiers (e.g. cultivar and germplasms identifiers) between omics data repositories, such as EVA for genotyping, and phenomics datasets.

Description of work

Activity 1: FAIRification of existing datasets (2.0 PMs) (*Lead: Daniel Arend (DE); Members: Cyril Pommier (FR), Isabelle Alic (FR), Timothee Cezard (EMBL-EBI), Sebastian Beier (DE), Matthijs Brouwer (NL). M13-20.*)

In this Activity, we will focus on the FAIRification of existing datasets, in particular the DROPS (<https://doi.org/10.15454/IASSTN>) and AGENT datasets (<https://dx.doi.org/10.5447/ipk/2023/20>) as well as selected datasets from other important crops (see below). We will also extend our efforts to other databases, e.g. datasets published in PHIS (<http://www.phis.inrae.fr/>) and support export of RO-Crates from EVA studies.

Main objectives:

1. Quantify the work necessary to produce machine-actionable FAIR datasets using RO-Crate from existing datasets.
2. Provide reference examples of standards adoption that demonstrate the FAIR process for both data producers and data repositories using RO-Crate.

Tasks:

T1.1: Assess the selected datasets to understand their structure, metadata requirements and current level of standardisation.

T1.2: Develop a detailed plan for converting these datasets to RO-Crate format to ensure compliance with FAIR principles.

T1.3: Conduct conversion of the selected datasets to RO-Crate and identify best practices and potential challenges.

T1.4: Adopt RO-Crate packaging in EVA as a use case for data repositories.

At the end of Activity 1, we will have a clear understanding of the effort required to produce machine-actionable datasets and lay the groundwork for subsequent work packages focussing on guidelines, adoption and dissemination of FAIR practices within the Plant Sciences.

Activity 2: Updating the documentation of standards, RDM guidelines, and checklists (3.5 PMs) (*Lead: Timothee Cezard (EMBL-EBI); Members: Cyril Pommier (FR), Isabelle Alic (FR), Daniel Arend (DE), Sebastian Beier (DE), Philippe Rocca-Serra (UK). M18-M24).*

The RDMKit 'Plant Sciences' page is used as the entry point to the RDM documentation used by the Community and beyond. It already includes documentation of plant data standards and tools. This Activity will update them in collaboration with the ELIXIR RDM Community to include an explicit and user-friendly decision tree that guides users to the relevant RDM resources. We will create and update the dataset FAIRification recipes referenced by the RDMKit. Finally, we will include relevant Activity 1 results in the MIAPPE standard documentation and generate updated mappings between other data standards (ISA, RO-Crate, BrAPI, Bioschemas). Activity 2 will provide researchers with a comprehensive resource within the RDMkit that will facilitate informed decisions and adoption to aid findability, reproducibility and reusability thanks to data standards, by presenting mappings and practical use cases for MIAPPE, BrAPI, ISA, Bioschemas and RO-Crate. In addition, the documentation and sample data of the standards will be expanded and harmonised with the latest versions.

Main objectives:

1. Expand the 'Plant Sciences' domain page in RDMkit (https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_sciences) as a one-stop-shop for Plant Science researchers seeking information on data standards and practices.
2. Develop and maintain links to and from relevant external websites (e.g. ELIXIR Plant Science Community, miappe.org, brapi.org, etc...) that provide detailed resources on data standards and related topics.
3. Update existing documentation and checklists to include Activity 1 results.

Tasks:

T2.1: Review and update existing documentation and checklists for dataset FAIRification.

T2.2: Design and implementation of a decision tree interface that guides researchers through the selection of appropriate dataset FAIRification guidelines based on their specific requirements.

T2.3: Update and development of mappings and guidelines for the integration of MIAPPE, BrAPI, ISA, Bioschemas and RO-Crate standards.

T2.4: Cross reference the RDMKit 'Plant Sciences' domain page to and from relevant websites (ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community page, FAIRsharing collection page <https://fairsharing.org/4741>) to increase its visibility and improve the number and quality of referenced resources. Recipes, in the form of Jupyter notebooks, will be added to the FAIR Cookbook.

T2.5: Write preprint on plant data FAIRification.

Activity 3: Extend the plant data discovery portal FAIDARE with new RO-Crate resources (1.75 PMs) (*Lead: Cyril Pommier (FR); Members: Daniel Arend (DE), Timothee Cezard (EMBL-EBI). M13-M24*).

The FAIDARE (<https://urgi.versailles.inra.fr/faidare/>) crop and agronomy data discovery portal is already able to index data resources using BrAPI or through data discovery files in a web folder (<https://urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/faidare/join>). The existing data indexing service will be extended to process RO-Crates for datasets. This enhancement will significantly improve the findability, accessibility and granularity of valuable datasets within FAIDARE. By the end of Activity 3, we will have significantly expanded the scope and usability of FAIDARE by including RO-Crate-enabled datasets, thereby improving the overall discoverability and accessibility of plant and agricultural data. This work will help to consolidate FAIDARE as the European plant data portal for researchers looking for FAIR data in the field of Plant Sciences and Agronomy.

Main objectives:

1. Extend FAIDARE's indexing capabilities to include RO-Crate data containers to ensure they are searchable and accessible via the FAIDARE data portal.
2. Improve the indexation of repositories such as PLANTdataHub, Dataverse, Zenodo and other relevant data repositories that provide RO-Crate data containers.
3. Demonstrate practical benefits of the FAIRification of dataset using RO-Crate.

Tasks:

T3.1: Development and implementation of methods for indexing RO-Crate data containers within the FAIDARE platform.

T3.2: Establish connections and integration pathways with external repositories hosting RO-Crate datasets to enable seamless data discovery and access via FAIDARE.

Activity 4: Dissemination and Training (1.25 PMs) (Lead: Sebastian Beier (DE); Members: Cyril Pommier (FR), Isabelle Alic (FR), Daniel Arend (DE), Timothee Cezard (EMBL-EBI). M18-M24).

This Activity will disseminate the project results and provide comprehensive training to promote awareness and adoption of data standards and FAIR practices in the Plant Science community. At the end of Activity 4, we maximise the impact of the project by effectively disseminating knowledge and providing a webinar that empowers researchers to incorporate FAIR data principles into their work, thereby increasing FAIR data management and accessibility in the field of Plant Sciences.

Main objectives:

1. Presentations at conferences (including posters and talks) to showcase the project results, share best practice and engage with the wider scientific community.
2. Conduct a webinar to present the project results and demonstrate the adoption of FAIR practices in Plant Data Management.

Tasks:

T4.1: Prepare and deliver presentations at relevant conferences to disseminate project findings, raise awareness and encourage collaboration within the plant science community.

T4.2: Organising and conducting a webinar for researchers, breeders and data managers to present and demonstrate the project results and to offer FAIR practices in Plant Data Management for adoption, building on material contributed to the FAIR Cookbook.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D4.1 (Activity 1)	Generate exemplary datasets as reference RO-Crates	DE-IPK	M18
D4.2 (Activity 2)	RDMkit pages updated and cross referenced on relevant websites	EMBL-EBI	M20
D4.3 (Activity 2)	Preprint on plant data FAIRification	DE-FZJU	M30

D4.4 (Activity 3)	Extension of FAIDARE Indexing (use PLANTdataHUB as use case), extension to other relevant repositories prepared (Dataverse, Zenodo)	FR-INRAE	M30
D4.5 (Activity 4)	Webinar on guidelines	DE-FZJU	M30

Outcomes and impact

The HARVEST project aims to significantly advance data management in plant research by integrating specific standards (such as MIAPPE and BrAPI) with generic standards (ISA and RO-Crate). It builds on previous initiatives such as ELIXIR IS FONDUE & INCREASING, H2020 AGENT, HE AgroServ & PHENET and the ongoing NFDIs DataPLANT, FAIRagro and NFDI4Biodiversity.

Past activities, including BioHackathons, have highlighted the need for more robust exemplification of MIAPPE with reference datasets and increased adoption of MIAPPE within the RO-Crate framework. The HARVEST project addresses these challenges by undertaking a sustained effort over an extended period of time.

The expected outcomes of HARVEST include easier adoption of best practices, improved data reusability and better data discoverability in plant sciences. This will help to streamline data management processes and promote collaboration and knowledge sharing. Additionally, HARVEST will harmonise information on FAIRification of plant data in various resources, including the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community site, FAIRsharing and others, with a central entry point in the RDMkit. Updates and enhancements to platforms such as RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook, FAIRsharing and related resources will contribute to a coherent and accessible framework for FAIRification of plant data and its management. For instance, the FAIR Cookbook will be enriched by incorporating Jupyter notebooks to demonstrate FAIRification and showcase how such processes will look like in practice.

The impact of the HARVEST project goes beyond ELIXIR by facilitating the dissemination and adoption of ELIXIR-promoted interoperability standards and initiatives in the field of research data management. HARVEST will provide exemplar datasets from DROPS, AGENT and other important crop species, providing a demonstration for other projects like PHENET, thus encouraging broader adoption of FAIR practices for data producers. Similarly, HARVEST will also demonstrate the potential of RO-Crate exports of datasets from EVA studies and serve as an example for other repositories to adopt similar practices in the future. One of the advantages of having experimental data and metadata in an RO-Crate is also the possibility of direct import into workflow systems such as the Galaxy platform (usegalaxy.eu), allowing researchers to run bioinformatics pipelines directly on the FAIRified data. In addition, the preprint publication, the webinar

session and the central entry point at RDMkit will play an important role in raising awareness and promoting the adoption of FAIR data principles and standards beyond the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community. We will communicate this progress to relevant stakeholders within AgBioData, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and actively engage them during the development. These efforts will facilitate broader engagement and collaboration between the different communities in the field of research data management.

Work Package 5 - Odyssey: Connecting molecular and geographical biodiversity data

WP 5	Lead Partner: GR-DUTH, NO-NMBU
	Start month - End month: M13-M30
WP Partnership	
GR-DUTH, Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou, Lead (WP and Activity 4) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 2 and Activity 3)	
NO-NMBU, Helle Tessand Baalsrud, Lead (WP) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 3 and Activity 4), Thu-Hien To, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 3), Lars Grønvold, Member (Activity 2 and Activity 3), Gareth Benjamin Gillard, Member (Activity 2 and Activity 3), Arturo VeraPonce de Leon, Member (Activity 3)	
GR-HCMR, Evangelos Pafilis, Lead (Activity 1 and Activity 2) , Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4), Nefeli Venetsianou, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2), Alexios Loukas, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2)	
GR-CERTH, Fotis Psomopoulos, Lead (Activity 3) , Member (Activity 2 and Activity 4), Nikolaos Pechlivanis, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2 and Activity 3), Anastasia Anastasiadou, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2 and Activity 3)	
Total	

Objectives

The project's scope is to develop a web portal that will enable researchers, stakeholders and citizens to navigate the molecular biodiversity data in a user-friendly and informative way based on the geographic information of Greece and Norway. This interface will become a pilot application with the perspective to further develop the resources of the Biodiversity Community and the ELIXIR Nodes, enabling wider integration of more European countries .

Specific objectives:

- Utilising and connecting existing databases, web portals and applications harbouring and handling molecular biodiversity data, along with species geospatial, ecological and phenotypic data, as well as available information about threats, challenges, conservation status and in-place policies. The main challenge will be aligning and harmonising the metadata across sources. For example, there is no consistency in the geo/location metadata across disparate

repositories and databases, especially in terms of granularity (e.g. there are cases where location only indicates country, and other cases where the exact GPS coordinates are mentioned). In this project we will try to harmonise this information so that data retrieved from multiple sources (such as GBIF and ENA) can be used in a seamless manner. To this end, we will also explore state-of-the-art NLP methods (incl. LLMs). However, we won't be assessing the validity of the metadata, such as location data, i.e. we won't perform error correction.

- Pilot the implemented framework by connecting resources, expertise and know-how from two different ELIXIR Nodes, representing two biodiversity rich regions in Europe (Nordic and Mediterranean) as well as differences in government and infrastructure relevant for molecular biodiversity, by utilising the existing networks in Greece (Molecular Biodiversity Greece Community - MBGC) and Norway (The Norwegian Biodiversity Working Group - NBWG), as hubs for exchange and meet. This will significantly strengthen and expand the biodiversity related efforts of the two Nodes.
- Leveraging the experience from the Norwegian and Greek ELIXIR Nodes to create and share training materials to increase the use of genetics and omics data in combination with geographical data both in basic and applied sciences such as conservation biology.
- Enhancing the availability of the existing documentation about the spatial genomic diversity patterns to biodiversity researchers, conservation scientists and decision makers and therefore bridging the gap between these groups.
- Increasing awareness about the importance of genomic information for biodiversity at all levels, by providing comprehensive and accessible information.
- Providing a use case that will benefit the ELIXIR Biodiversity Community, as it can be expanded and connected with various ELIXIR Platforms (Data, Training, Tools), Communities (Microbiome, Plant Sciences, Food and Nutrition), as well as ELIXIR's external partners and projects.

This proposal specifically targets the core goals of the BFSP Priority Area mission, by providing a framework to make biodiversity molecular data more accessible to the wider community while enabling full customisation to support the particular needs of a Node or a Community. While there are major databases and efforts in place that aim to provide this harmonised access to high-quality data, there is still a lot of information that is being deposited in non-specialized databases (such as ENA), or even only in national and local repositories. The main output of this effort will be to implement a reusable framework, that can be deployed by individual users and/or institutions, that will enable metadata curation, semi-automated harmonisation, and visualisation of data from multiple user-defined sources, while also offering the creation of AI-ready datasets as export function.

Odyssey will be leveraging the interoperability standards for metadata in the underlying repository, while taking advantage of the existing Core Data Resources (such as the European Nucleotide Archive - ENA: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility - GBIF: <https://www.gbif.org/>) as primary data providers. Specifically, the framework implemented in this project, closely following the ELIXIR Tools Software Best Practices, will enable individual users to directly query ENA and GBIF, in order to retrieve molecular biodiversity data relevant to their study. Although the data itself will not be stored locally, the main advantage of this framework is to enable local storage and curation of the respective metadata, by offering a seamless and semi-automated way of annotating. Beyond ENA and GBIF, we will be reviewing additional sources of data, such as BGE (and its connections to iBOL/BOLD/Earth Biogenome Project). Ultimately, the effort of this project will be analogous to GoAT (<https://goat.genomehubs.org/>), connecting molecular metadata from multiple sources and optimising both query and visualisation methods to align to a nation's community requirements. Finally, the framework will be demonstrated using the two involved Nodes (GR/NO) as pilot cases, but the ambition is for this framework to be used across all ELIXIR Nodes.

Moreover, all software produced under this project will closely follow the Tools Platform software best practices recommendations, and adhere to the expectations set by projects such as ELIXIR-STEERS and EVERSE for high quality software. Additionally, the project will establish a continuous feedback mechanism with the Biodiversity Community, to ensure that the final output will be adopted and re-used by the individual Nodes - a process that will include organising at least one workshop / hackathon for members of ELIXIR to participate and contribute. Finally, the project will fully build on the existing efforts of the MBGC and NBWG in Greece and Norway.

Description of work

Activity 1: Connecting the Dots - Data Gathering (2.25 PMs) (*Lead: Evangelos Pafilis (GR), Helle Tessand Baalsrud (NO); Members: Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou (GR), Thu-Hien To, Arturo VeraPonce de Leon (NO), Alexios Loukas, Nefeli Venetsianou (GR), Nikolaos Pechlivanis, Anastasia Anastasiadou (GR). M13-M30*).

We will mine data and metadata for Greece and Norway from two different databases, ENA and GBIF. ENA contains various sequence data from barcodes to full genomes, sometimes with geographical location. GBIF contains biodiversity occurrence data, of which only some of it refers to the geographical location of molecular data. We will retrieve and connect these types of data, which will be overlaid on maps and organised in terms of taxonomic groups, populations, habitats and geographical regions. This will include harmonising geographical metadata from ENA, as different formats have been used.

Incrementally more data sources will be explored. These can include datasets from Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) as well as retrieval of pertinent biodiversity literature from BiodiversityPMC. By adding geographical reference to molecular data, the integration of further geospatial, ecological and phenotypic data could be investigated as a preparation for future functionality. Maps of protected areas as well as land cover charts, for example, could offer key information about threats, challenges, conservation status and in-place policies.

Tasks:

T1.1: Plan with ENA and GBIF the gaps of information that can be filled.

T1.2: Connect to up-to-date biodiversity literature information and metadata mining for Greece and Norway.

Activity 2: Application Design and Implementation (3.60 PMs) (*Lead: Evangelos Pafilis (GR), Lars Grønvold (NO); Members: Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou, Fotis Psomopoulos, Nikolaos Pechlivanis, Anastasia Anastasiadou (GR), Gareth Benjamin Gillard (NO), Alexios Loukas, Nefeli Venetsianou (GR). M13-M30).*

The members of the proposal will define the key functionalities to be facilitated by the portal. Such domain expertise in collaboration with software developers will be translated into an application, aiming at answering to the needs of the biodiversity community in a simple-to-use way, excluding the need for advanced knowledge of querying databases.

Working in parallel with and utilising data sourced from Activity1 a dedicated unified repository will be implemented, that will contain the harmonised data as well as additional fields necessary for further study (geographical coordinates, sequences, etc). Additionally, a graphical interface will be developed, named Odyssey, to delve into biodiversity information. Odyssey will undergo development to ensure accessibility to users. This development will be divided into backend and frontend design and development. To this end, enhancements applied to the existing prototype (accessible at shinyapps.io/odyssey) to seamlessly integrate Activity2 front-end components designed for the presentation of the collected data. R Shiny will serve as the primary web application technology. The related software components will be openly available.

Tasks:

T2.1: Adding geographical context (WG84 coordinates, altitude) on database content, such as sequence data from ENA and biodiversity occurrence data from GBIF.

T2.2: Designing and implementing backend functionalities including tasks such as integrating Activity1 data sources to efficiently store and manage molecular biodiversity

data, implementing database schemas, optimising server-side processes, and integrating data cleaning processes to ensure data quality and integrity.

T2.3: Implementing frontend features including User Interface Refinement within the Odyssey web platform through intuitive navigation elements, descriptive statistics, and visualisations, alongside R Shiny Implementation to incorporate dynamic and interactive features via modular design, while ensuring Open Accessibility through GitHub to foster transparency and collaboration within the research community.

Activity 3: Dissemination and Training (3.15 PMs) (*Lead: Fotis Psomopoulos (GR), Arturo VeraPonce de Leon (NO); Members: Evangelos Pafilis (GR), Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou (GR), Nikolaos Pechlivanis (GR), Anastasia Anastasiadou (GR), Helle Tessand Baalsrud, Lars Grønvold, Gareth Benjamin Gillard, Thu-Hien To (NO). M13-M30).*)

Dissemination, training and promotion actions, inviting users from the biodiversity research and applied conservation community in Greece and Norway. These will include:

- One kickoff online meeting and workshop announcing Odyssey and describing the functions to members of MBGC in Greece and NBWG in Norway, including also stakeholders (national and local conservation agencies).
- A scientific communication section in the Odyssey portal, supported by a channel on an open-access platform with demonstration and promotion video material.
- Open-access publications, presentations in biodiversity related conferences and meetings.
- Training material, produced and distributed following the FAIR principles and demonstrating Odyssey, its underlying machinery and its use, presented within relevant postgraduate programmes in Greece and Norway.
- Complementary to the automated methods of Activity1, Activity2, and on a need-only basis, georeference information for selected molecular datasets, will be further improved by community member curation. An online datathon will be organised to this end.
- Joint meetings with other ELIXIR Nodes and Communities / Platforms / Focus Groups. Specifically, and in order to strengthen the planned connection to ENA and GBIF, we will ensure that representatives from these resources will be invited to attend and contribute to at least one of these events.

Tasks:

T3.1: Showcase application and promote best practices for taxonomy and geographical data annotation when working with sequence data. Host training material online with Activity3 implementation.

T3.2 Create a public repository (e.g GitHub) with manuals and tutorials about using Odyssey to explore biodiversity as training material using FAIR principles.

T3.3 Develop a workshop showing the application of Odyssey with real data to the biodiversity community. The workshop will be streamed online to reach a wider audience.

Activity 4: Project Management (1.50 PMs) (Lead: Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou (GR), Helle Tessand Baalsrud (NO); Members: Evangelos Pafilis (GR), Fotis Psomopoulos (GR). M13-M30).

This Activity aims to coordinate the research team scientifically and administratively, implement the project's tasks and activities within the time frame, manage the project's finances and the software produced. These activities involve coordinating the project implementation by assessing the outputs based on the objectives, tracking the budget and possible changes, resolving conflicts and creating a risk management plan. The deliverables and milestones will be constantly checked to follow the programme schedule.

Moreover, a dedicated in-person workshop open to the entire community will be organised in the first half of the project, in order to push forward the development process (Activity1/Activity2), as well as establish an outline of the expected training material.

Tasks:

T4.1: Personnel exchange for training and collaboration, meetings, publications, reports.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D5.1 (Activity 1)	Report on the overview of relevant molecular biodiversity data in Greece and Norway	GR-HCMR	M30
D5.2 (Activity 2)	Back-end (database, schema, etc)	NO-NMBU	M30
D5.3 (Activity 2)	Front-end (shiny app, GitHub repo)	GR-CERTH	M30
D5.4 (Activity 3)	Run a virtual training event	GR-CERTH	M29
D5.5 (Activity 4)	Final project report	GR-DUTH	M30
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month

M5.1 (Activity 1)	Successfully implemented queries to ENA and GBIF	GR-HCMR	M18
M5.2 (Activity 2)	First demo of the Odyssey framework	NO-NMBU	M24
M5.3 (Activity 3)	Training material prepared and delivered in GitHub	GR-CERTH	M24
M5.4 (Activity 4)	Organise an open community event to demonstrate the new resource and its features getting feedback on the user requirements	NO-NMBU	M27

Outcomes and impact

Odyssey's ambition is to serve as a pivotal tool in bridging gaps within biodiversity research, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and connecting scientific endeavours with conservation efforts. By making molecular biodiversity data accessible to researchers, stakeholders, and the public, this tool will facilitate informed decision-making, ultimately promoting conservation practices. Below are concrete outcomes and impact.

Outcomes

- Overview of molecular biodiversity data connected to geographical metadata in Norway and Greece.
- "Odyssey", an application to visualise, query and research relevant molecular data on a geographical map. This application will be a prototype developed for Norway and Greece, with the goal of expanding this effort to encompass the entire world.
- Strengthening of biodiversity related activities in Elixir-NO and Elixir-GR

Impact

- Science: Odyssey will have a profound impact on the scientific community as one of the main obstacles in molecular biodiversity research is to connect and harmonise different types of data. This is not a trivial matter, and by developing a web portal in the form of a user-friendly interface that allows federated searches of molecular databases and geographical databases will facilitate increased scientific output in this growing field.
- Biodiversity monitoring and conservation: There is currently an increase in the use of molecular data to catalogue and monitor biodiversity across the world, which is especially important to gain insights into understudied taxonomic groups and ecosystems. Odyssey will provide a user-friendly tool to study the geographical prevalence of molecular data, which could be used to better

harness existing data as well as inform stakeholders which taxa or geographical regions with significant gaps.

- The Biodiversity Community - ELIXIR: Collaboration and cooperation between Nodes with distinct needs and expertise is an integral theme to Odyssey, fostering complementarity and knowledge exchange within the ELIXIR network. By design, the implemented framework will enable direct reuse and adoption by various communities across the Nodes, strengthening networks and fostering collaboration with strategic partners. By involving diverse stakeholders and leveraging existing initiatives (e.g., by inviting experts from different ELIXIR Nodes to meetings and workshops at all stages of the project), Odyssey enhances the capacity of the ELIXIR Biodiversity Community to address complex challenges and advance molecular biodiversity research on a transnational scale.
- Society: The main mission of Odyssey is to lower the barrier and facilitate biodiversity research, by harnessing molecular data in conjunction with geographic information and making the respective data available to the wider community. By integrating diverse datasets and employing advanced visualisation methods, it promises to enable a more in-depth understanding of molecular biodiversity in regions of interest - and always depending on the community it serves.

Work Package 6 - BioDiv-FAIR-Checker: Raising FAIRness of European biodiversity data through ELIXIR-aligned standards, services, and training

WP 6	Lead Partner: FR-CNRS
	Start month - End month: M25-M36
WP Partnership	
FR-CNRS, Alban Gaignard, Lead (WP and Activity 3) , Member (Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
CH-SIB, Rob Waterhouse, Lead (Activity 2) , Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4), Christian de Guttry, Member (Activity 1), Chiara Bortoluzzi, Member (Activity 1)	
UK-UNIMAN, Carole Goble, Lead (Activity 4) , Member (Activity 2 and Activity 3), Nick Juty, Member (Activity 3)	
FR-IFB, Frédéric De Lamotte, (ActivMemberity 2-3-4), Erwan Corre, Member (Activity 2-3-4)	
Total	

Objectives

Biodiversity research is generating an unprecedented volume and variety of digital objects at an unparalleled speed, ranging from whole-genome assemblies to specimen images and long-term ecosystem observation datasets. Yet, the specialised nature of these resources confounds generic FAIR assessment tools, which were designed primarily for homogeneous data or computational workflows. FAIR indicators like those proposed by the Research Data Alliance are provided from a high-level perspective that can be open to interpretation and are not always realistic to particular environments like multidisciplinary repositories (Gómez and Bernal, 2023). This is a gap that EOSC FAIR Working Groups have highlighted (EC 2020). Consequently, well-curated and highly valuable datasets from initiatives such as the European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA), the Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN), and the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo) often receive deceptively low FAIR scores, are insufficiently acknowledged within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and are reused less frequently (Wilkinson et al., 2016; Petrosyan et al., 2023). The BioDiv-FC project addresses this gap by extending the scope of the open-source FAIR-Checker tool (Gaignard et al. 2023, supported by Elixir-FR SDP) with domain-aware metrics, machine-actionable recommendations, and easy integration into research

infrastructures, thereby transforming FAIR evaluation from an aspiration into an operational, community-owned reality.

BioDiv-FC aims to institutionalise rigorous, domain-specific FAIR assessment as a standard practice across the broad and diverse spectrum of biodiversity data, encompassing fields from genomics to ecology and related disciplines. We will:

1. Design semantic rule-sets, formalised in SHACL (W3C standard), checking that essential metadata is present for taxonomic provenance, geospatial precision, and voucher-specimen linkage;
2. Ensure that metadata complies with community standards and captures the nuances of Minimum Information lists, (e.g. MIxS, Darwin Core, ABCDDNA);
3. Engage with the community through hackathons, workshops, and meetings to ensure that proposed solutions reflect the community's needs while encouraging their adoption.

Description of work

Activity 1: Project management (3 PMs) (*Lead: Rob Waterhouse (CH); Members: Christian de Guttery, Chiara Bortoluzzi (CH). M25-M36*).

The project will adopt an agile governance model. Three-month development cycles, leading to public releases, and an open GitHub issue tracker will improve transparency and invite external contributions. By the mid-term milestone, a public beta version will deliver FAIR scores for at least one hundred pilot datasets across genomic, specimen, and environmental data modalities, enabling early feedback and iterative refinement.

Our travel and meeting plan is designed to make the most of existing ELIXIR gatherings while promoting close collaboration across the project. We will start with a kick-off meeting during the ELIXIR face-to-face meetings in February 2026, providing an early opportunity to align goals and build connections. As the project progresses, we plan to meet again at the ELIXIR All-Hands meeting in Lyon, where we will participate in a biodiversity workshop and co-organize a hackathon to encourage hands-on exchange. We aim to close the project with an Elixir staff exchange, creating an environment for deeper knowledge sharing and discussion about future steps.

Activity 2: Specify minimal and recommended biodiversity metadata (2 PMs) (*Lead: Rob Waterhouse (CH); Members: Chiara Bortoluzzi (CH), Christian De Guttery (CH), Alban Gaignard (FR), Frédéric De Lamotte (FR), Erwan Corre (FR), Carole Goble (UK), Nick Jury (UK). M25-M36*).

Task T1 aims to identify, harmonise, and publish minimal and recommended metadata fields for genomics, specimen, and ecological time-series datasets.

Work programme

We will run a requirements process with ERGA, DiSSCo, eLTER, LifeWatch ERIC, iBOL and GGBN to (i) collect needs via short surveys and focused consultations; (ii) review existing templates (ERGA manifest, DiSSCo Digital Specimen profiles, ENA/BioSamples checklists) and FAIRsharing records; (iii) draft a cross-domain “core” plus domain extensions, each split into minimal vs recommended requirements ; (iv) circulate v0.x for comment, resolve issues, and publish v1.0 human-readable specification and field catalogue, to be consumed by T2 (implementation) and T3 (engagement/training).

Methods

We will (i) maintain a field catalogue (CSV/YAML) with term label, definition, rationale, order of importance, example, allowed value source (e.g., NCBI Taxonomy, GBIF backbone, GeoNames/Gazetteers, Unit Ontology), identifier patterns (DOI, ORCID, specimen PID), and licence expectations; (ii) produce crosswalk matrices MxS/Darwin Core/ABCDDNA indicating exact/partial/no match and transformation notes; (iii) provide acceptance criteria in plain language such as “geospatial precision ≤ 100 m; time in ISO-8601; taxon resolved to GBIF key), suitable for later machine formalisation in T2; (iv) use open governance with GitHub issues, public changelog, and semantic versioning. Scope is limited to specification only (no code, tests, or pilots in T1)

Risks

To mitigate low engagement or slow consensus, we will participate in scheduled community meetings, recognise contributors, and, if necessary, publish a “core-v0” derived from existing standards. Cross-domain conflicts will be addressed through a layered design (core plus extensions) with a documented rationale, and report unresolved issues to TDWG task groups. To avoid over-complexity, we will supply one-page “minimum viable” checklists and filled-in examples, keeping recommended fields clearly optional. To prevent scope inflation, we will enforce RACI boundaries and defer any implementation or registration activities to T2/T3. To manage potential timeline delays, we will move unresolved items to a deferred v1.1.

Activity 3: Implement biodiversity-specific FAIR assessment metrics (3 PMs) (*Lead: Alban Gaignard (FR); Members: Rob Waterhouse (CH), Chiara Bortoluzzi (CH), Christian De Guttry (CH), Carole Goble (UK), Nick Juty (UK), Frédéric De Lamotte (FR), Erwan Corre (FR). M25-M36).*

Task T2 aims at transforming biodiversity-specific recommendations (D1.1) into a machine-actionable metadata profile to be evaluated within FAIR-Checker.

Work programme

BioDiv-FC relies on mature foundations. FAIR-Checker v1.3 already ingests RDFa and JSON-LD; where extensions focus on domain rules, user-experience refinements, and cloud deployment. We will i) leverage FAIR-Signposting (Wilkinson et al., 2024) to consume metadata outside landing web pages, ii) integrate domain-specific metrics as well as domain-specific web pages in a specific FAIR-Checker plugin.

BioDiv-FC will work to expose a RESTful API, a command-line interface, and an interactive dashboard, allowing researchers, data stewards, and data repositories themselves to quickly diagnose FAIR shortcomings and provide customised steps for improvement. All code will be released under an open source license (e.g. FAIR-Checker is under the MIT license); versions, training materials, and container recipes will be archived on Zenodo with digital object identifiers (DOIs), guaranteeing long-term accessibility and reproducibility.

Methods

The FAIR-Checker metadata harvesting module will be extended with FAIR-Signposting to consume metadata which is not directly exposed in the web page. Indeed, in some cases, metadata can be stored in separate remote files or can be stored inside an archive as proposed in the RO-crate approach.

Bioschemas already specifies a [BioSample metadata profile](#). This profile will be extended to fit biodiversity needs and will be translated into SHACL shapes for automated validation within FAIR-Checker.

Risks

In the case of delayed D1.1 due to underestimated effort of reaching consensus with the biodiversity community, T2 will start from the existing BioSample Bioschemas profile.

Activity 4: Community engagement (2 PMs) (*Lead: Carole Goble (UK); Members: Nick Juty (UK), Alban Gaignard (FR), Frédéric De Lamotte (FR), Erwan Corre (FR), Rob Waterhouse (CH), Chiara Bortoluzzi (CH), Christian De Guttry (CH). M25-M36*).

The goal of task T3 is to ensure community engagement along the project duration .

Work programme

We will integrate community co-creation and outreach at every stage. Hackathons, hosted alternately by the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB) and the University of Manchester (UNIMAN), will bring together representatives from LifeWatch ERIC, eLTER, iBOL, and others. Tutorial videos will be integrated into the ELIXIR TeSS training portal. Community support will be achieved through identifying representatives participating in

the hackathons to act as points of contact. A reactivated Working Group for Sample and BioSample specifications within Bioschemas is already advancing work on these 'types'.

We will also drive a sustainable data-management culture by registering the BioDiv-FC solutions as an EOSC Exchange service, and aligning with the evolving FAIR Digital Object framework promoted by the Environmental Research Infrastructure cluster (ENVRI-FAIR).

Community engagement is both a means and an end for BioDiv-FC. Working with members of DiSSCo, eLTER, and LifeWatch ERIC (see letters of support) builds the direct connection to millions of digital specimens and thousands of ecosystem time-series datasets for benchmark evaluation, while contributions to the project from EMBL–EBI and ELIXIR (see support letter) will ensure that the extended tool can interrogate genomics datasets at the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) without breaching rate limits.

Methods

To ensure broad uptake and effective use of the tool, we will organize and schedule a number of online webinars to demonstrate functionalities, complemented by “Ask Me Anything” workshop(s) to gather feedback and address user questions. These will also showcase our activities and reach out to broader communities. For long-term integration, the tool will be embedded into the ELIXIR RDM ecosystem, leveraging our connections with the RDM community and ELIXIR Interoperability platform, ensuring interoperability and alignment with community practices. Training materials and events will initially be registered in the ERGA Knowledge Hub and TeSS to maximize visibility, and resulting metadata profiles will be registered in FAIRsharing.

Risks

Risks include uneven community participation or slow uptake, scheduling clashes with existing ELIXIR/community events, outreach fatigue, accessibility barriers (language/time zones), scope drift into T1/T2, and delays in external listings (TeSS, FAIRsharing, ERGA Knowledge Hub). Fallbacks: co-locate activities with established meetings, appoint key community representatives to help organise participation and encourage participation, provide multilingual/asynchronous materials (recordings, short how-tos) as needed, rotate session times, to accommodate wider participation, and direct feedback to T1 (spec) or T2 (implementation) under RACI boundaries. We will deliver a lightweight onboarding kit and a public test environment for a safe trial. If registrations slip, interim guidance will be published on GitHub/Zenodo and cross-linked via the ELIXIR RDM ecosystem until listings are confirmed.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D6.1 (Activity 2)	Minimal and recommended biodiversity metadata fields	CH-SIB	M30
D6.2 (Activity 3)	Biodiv FAIR metrics implementation	FR-CNRS	M31
D6.3 (Activity 4)	Biodiv metadata profile (Bioschemas profile + SHACL rules)	UK-UoM	M33
D6.4 (Activity 3)	FAIR-Checker biodiversity plugin	FR-CNRS	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M6.1 (Activity 2)	Discussion forum for multiple biodiversity communities to express their shared needs	CH-SIB	M26
M6.2 (Activity 3)	A FAIRness evaluation of representative entries in ENA, BioSample, and DiSSCo	FR-CNRS	M26
M6.3 (Activity 4)	Expose Biodiv-FC through the RDMkit ecosystem	UK-UoM	M31

Outcomes and impact

BioDiv-FC is designed to enhance the value of biodiversity datasets by tailoring quality assessments to the specific needs of each discipline rather than using generic rules. It will use specialized checkers for genomics, specimen records, and ecological time-series to highlight the most relevant metadata. For example, it will focus on taxonomic identifiers in genomics, specimen links in collections, and temporal consistency in ecological data. The tool will turn these checks into practical recommendations, helping data providers improve their datasets throughout a project's lifecycle. Repository managers will also gain a clear, transparent foundation for their curation policies. As FAIR scores improve, datasets become easier to discover, compare, and integrate. Rich, well-structured and interoperable metadata increases the likelihood that resources are indexed by aggregation services, within and beyond Elixir, such as EOSC Search & Discovery and OpenAIRE, broadening their visibility far beyond the originating community. Interoperability also benefits downstream science: researchers can link sequence data to verified specimens, embed environmental context in comparative genomics, or combine long-term ecological time series without laborious reformatting.

By providing training resources and dedicated workshops, the project will engage and encourage researchers, with champions from the three main communities, to co-create,

test and increasingly adopt the developed solutions in their daily scientific work to create a more unified approach to biodiversity data management, fostering greater interoperability and consistency across disciplines. Existing community connections will be leveraged to ensure a wide reach, including with the ELIXIR Biodiversity Community (SIB PI co-leads), the ERGA community (SIB PI is ERGA chairperson) and the Biodiversity Genomics Europe Project (SIB and UNIMAN are partners), as well as the Biodiversity Meets Data project (SIB is a partner). As the tool helps identify datasets that are well-documented, properly formatted, and stored in accessible repositories, it will directly contribute to increasing the transparency and reproducibility of science.

Development work is anchored in ENVRI, engaging DiSSCo for specimen data, eLTER for ecological time-series datasets, and LifeWatch ERIC for virtual research environments, yet the architecture is co-designed with LS actors, ensuring that genomic use-cases, e.g. championed by ERGA and ELIXIR, can adopt the service without duplication of effort. DiSSCo gains an automated gatekeeper for Digital Specimens; eLTER can integrate the checker as a pre-ingestion step in its data portal; LifeWatch ERIC can surface FAIR badges directly in its analytical workspaces.

Transparent quality metrics will enable funding agencies to monitor compliance, publishers to mandate best practice, and educators to illustrate tangible benefits of data stewardship, thereby embedding FAIR thinking throughout the research lifecycle. Societal benefits flow naturally from improved data quality and accessibility. Policy-makers will gain quicker access to harmonised biodiversity indicators, bolstering evidence-based conservation strategies; citizen scientists will find authoritative datasets more easily, enhancing public engagement; and industry innovators will exploit interoperable data streams for biotechnological applications, stimulating economic growth. By promoting open, reusable, and trustworthy data, outputs from the BioDiv-FC project will reinforce the EU's commitment to excellence, transparency, and inclusivity in science.

Work Package 7 - Building FAIR metadata standards for non-human pathogen genomic and phenotypic data

WP 7	Lead Partner: <i>NO-UiT</i>
	Start month - End month: M25-M36
WP Partnership	
NO-UiT, Erik Hjerde, Lead (WP and Activity 1) , Member (Activity 1 and Activity 4)	
ES-ISCI, Isabel Cuesta, Lead (Activity 2) , Member (Activity 1), Sara Monzón, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2)	
PT-BioData, Teresa Nogueira, Lead (Activity 3)	
DE-FZJU, Daniel Wibberg, Lead (Activity 4)	
Total	

Objectives

Metadata is essential for organising, structuring, and managing large datasets. It enables discovery, integration, and interpretation, and is key to making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). Well-curated metadata ensures reproducibility, supports secondary analyses, and maximises long-term research value.

ELIXIR's Scientific Programme 2024–2028 stresses the integration of molecular data across biodiversity, food security, and pathogen domains, recognising the importance of pathogens beyond humans—those affecting wildlife, animals, and plants. While human pathogen metadata standards are mature and repository-integrated, non-human pathogen data remain fragmented, with inconsistent practices across veterinary, agricultural, and environmental sectors. Our proposal addresses this gap by developing and piloting FAIR-aligned metadata standards for non-human pathogens, directly supporting BFSP priorities.

Historically, infectious disease research has prioritised human pathogens. Global health strategies, funding, and data infrastructures focused on human health, with robust systems for annotation and deposition established well before COVID-19. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al.,) illustrate how the biomedical domain has benefited from coordinated efforts on quality, interoperability, and discoverability.

This imbalance is also reflected in repositories. For example, in the EBI Pathogens Portal, over three million samples are linked to host species, with about two-thirds from human

pathogens. Even these datasets face restrictions due to privacy, ethics, and confidentiality, with many held in silos or shared only in aggregate.

For non-human pathogens, barriers are greater. Veterinary datasets are often absent or underrepresented, with confidentiality concerns limiting deposition. In aquaculture, for example, publishing the presence of a pathogen could have major economic or reputational impacts, discouraging data sharing. Surveillance datasets may also be sparse or fragmented, making it possible to trace pathogens back to farms or regions despite anonymisation. To avoid this, providers often strip essential metadata such as farm identifiers, geographic codes, treatment history, or host information—reducing data utility for broader analysis.

As a result, large volumes of veterinary and environmental pathogen data remain inaccessible or poorly annotated (Kreienbrock et al.,). This asymmetry undermines One Health initiatives and hampers development of federated, AI-ready data ecosystems spanning human, animal, and environmental domains.

To promote adoption of harmonised standards, the project will provide authoring guidelines and training, enabling data producers to deposit genomic and phenotypic data into repositories such as the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), BioSamples, and BioStudies.

The project will be structured into four activities:

- Landscape analysis and gap assessment – review existing metadata standards for food, veterinary, plant, and environmental pathogens, benchmark against human frameworks, and identify key gaps.
- Metadata template development – co-design harmonised, ontology-aligned metadata templates with ELIXIR Communities, defining mandatory and optional fields.
- Pilot implementation – apply templates to selected datasets and deposit them into repositories to test feasibility, compatibility, and usability.
- Training and sustainability planning – deliver training, publish guidance materials, and prepare an adoption plan to ensure continued use of the templates beyond the project.

Description of work

Activity 1: Landscape Analysis and Gap Assessment (2.5 PMs) (*Lead: Erik Hjerde (NO); Members: Isabel Cuesta, Sara Monzón (ES). M25-M36.*)

We will review existing metadata standards and practices in veterinary, plant, and environmental pathogen domains, including MIxS, Darwin Core, ENVO, and

sector-specific guidelines. This review will be benchmarked against well-established human pathogen frameworks such as PHA4GE and INSDC checklists. Through consultation with domain experts and ELIXIR Communities, we will identify missing or inconsistently applied elements—such as host species/breed, crop variety, geographic precision, symptom descriptions, and treatment history—critical for cross-sector integration.

Activity 2: Metadata Template Development (3 PMs) (*Lead: Isabel Cuesta (ES); Members: Sara Monzón (ES). M25-M36.*)

Introduction

Building on the results of Activity 1, this activity will focus on co-developing harmonised metadata templates for non-human pathogens. While Activity 1 identifies existing standards and gaps, Activity 2 will translate those findings into concrete, implementable templates. This ensures that the templates are complementary to ongoing initiatives and avoid duplication of work.

Coordination with other initiatives

To maximise interoperability, we will engage with relevant ELIXIR Communities as well as external initiatives that already maintain metadata models. This includes ENA checklists, BioSamples/FEGA metadata model, and standards developed by the Genomics Standards Consortium, GSC (e.g. MIxS). The activity will assess whether existing checklists require updates or whether new templates are needed. We will follow repository and community guidelines to ensure that metadata produced here can be directly used for submissions to ENA, BioStudies, and related databases.

Development of templates

Using the gap analysis as a foundation, we will:

- Define mandatory and optional metadata fields for genomic and phenotypic data relevant to non-human pathogens.
- Align fields with established ontologies and controlled vocabularies such as GENEPIO, LOINC, ENVO, and SNOMED-CT.
- Implement the templates in both human-readable (spreadsheet/CSV) and machine-readable (JSON Schema, ISO-compliant formats) versions to facilitate adoption across different user groups.
- Ensure compatibility with repository submission pipelines by testing structure and format against ENA and BioStudies validators.

The templates will be prepared in modular form (e.g., pathogen, host, environment, phenotypic context), enabling adaptation to different use cases while maintaining consistency.

Activity 3: Pilot Implementation (2.5 PMs) *(Lead: Teresa Nogueira (PT). M25-M36).*

This activity will validate the harmonised metadata template developed in Activity 2 by applying it to real-world datasets from project partners.

Dataset Selection

Partners will be invited to propose candidate datasets during virtual coordination meetings. To maximise coverage, at least two distinct types of datasets will be selected (e.g. veterinary pathogen surveillance data such as Salmonella in poultry, and plant pathogen datasets such as fungal diseases in crops). Using diverse datasets will help to capture a broad range of metadata challenges.

Testing Process

Selected partners will apply the harmonised metadata template during dataset deposition to ENA or BioStudies, in collaboration with repository support teams. Each dataset will be tested independently by at least two individuals to ensure reproducibility and identify potential usability issues. Structured feedback will be collected from data providers, curators, and repository managers on both compatibility and user experience. Paired testers will then convene to consolidate their findings and highlight any challenges.

Evaluation

A final review meeting will be organised to discuss outcomes, refine the templates, and agree on recommendations for broader implementation.

Activity 4: Training, Dissemination, and Sustainability Planning (2.5 PMs) *(Lead: Daniel Wibberg (DE); Members: Erik Hjerde (NO). M25-M36).*

Introduction

To strengthen the stewardship and sharing of microbial research data, this activity will develop and deliver a comprehensive training course session and training material with a particular focus on data management strategies for non-human pathogen datasets. This activity builds on the successful annual “Maximizing the Potential of Microbial Research Data” course, which combines foundational Research Data Management (RDM) concepts with applied best practices tailored to microbial research. Here, ELIXIR Germany collaborates with NFDI4Microbiota, a consortium within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

Training Design: Core Course and Pathogen Data Session

Participants will receive interactive instruction on the research data lifecycle, FAIR data principles, and key aspects of effective RDM, with explicit emphasis on the unique

requirements of microbial research data. The course includes both expert-led presentations and practical hands-on exercises using tools such as RDMkit and DSW.

A dedicated session on non-human pathogen data will provide in-depth guidance on:

- Current metadata standards for non-human pathogen research,
- Implementation of FAIR principles in day-to-day workflows, and
- Step-by-step demonstration of repository submission for pathogen datasets.

Capacity Building and Long-Term Impact

To facilitate continued adoption, the activity will produce concise, reusable training materials and host at least one online training event (building on existing ELIXIR/NFDI course), complemented by a practical guidance document and adoption plan. These resources and templates will be promoted via ELIXIR channels and published in the Training eSupport System (TeSS) as well as Zenodo, supporting ELIXIR's long-term strategy for sustainable data management training. Moreover, recommendations will be provided for integration of the developed workflows and standards into ELIXIR's broader roadmap, encouraging harmonisation and uptake across the community beyond the project's lifetime.

This activity will improve capacity in the microbial research community for robust data management, with particular benefit to those working with sensitive or high-impact non-human pathogen data, and will contribute directly to ELIXIR's strategic goals in interoperability, data reuse, and scientific excellence.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D7.1 (Activity 1)	Publish gap analysis report	NO-UiT	M27
D7.2 (Activity 2)	Document collecting and comparing existing metadata models and draft schema design for non-human pathogens.	ES-ISCI	M28
D7.3 (Activity 2)	Publish harmonised metadata templates for non-human pathogens, aligned with ontologies and repository requirements.	ES-ISCI	M30
D7.4 (Activity 3)	Pilot datasets deposited with harmonised metadata	PT-BioDat	M34
D7.5 (Activity 3)	Short evaluation report documenting lessons learned and proposed improvements	PT-BioDat	M34
D7.6 (Activity 4)	Training Materials - Complete set of expert-led presentations, hands-on exercises, and reusable training	DE-FZJU	M35

	content for microbial data management, including a module focused on non-human pathogen data.		
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M7.1 (Activity 1)	Complete interviews with 10 domain experts	NO-UiT	M26
M7.2 (Activity 2)	Metadata model review completed and first draft schema structure agreed with partner communities	ES-ISCI	M28
M7.3 (Activity 2)	Draft templates validated for structure/compatibility with ENA and BioStudies submission pipelines.	ES-ISCI	M30
M7.4 (Activity 3)	Harmonised metadata templates tested and validated	PT-BioDat	M34
M7.5 (Activity 3)	Training Event - Deliver at least one online interactive training event, including presentations, hands-on exercises, and dedicated pathogen data session.	DE-FZJU	M36

Outcomes and impact

By the end of the 12-month project, ELIXIR will have a tested and community-validated metadata standard for non-human pathogen genomic and phenotypic data, aligned with international ontologies and repository requirements. This standard will be published in both human- and machine-readable formats, with clear guidance on its use. Selected pilot datasets will be deposited into repositories such as ENA, BioSamples, and BioStudies, demonstrating feasibility and interoperability.

Training materials and workshop recordings will be openly available via TeSS and Zenodo, enabling continued capacity building beyond the project. An adoption and sustainability plan will guide ELIXIR Nodes, communities, and partner organisations in integrating the templates into their workflows. The outcomes will lay the groundwork for broader uptake, future refinement, and potential expansion into global One Health initiatives, complementing efforts such as PHA4GE and NFDI4Microbiota.

This project will:

- Improve interoperability of non-human pathogen data across sectors, enabling One Health approaches to surveillance and research.
- Enhance discoverability and re-use of genomic and phenotypic data by aligning metadata capture with FAIR principles and repository requirements.
- Build community capacity by equipping researchers, data providers, and data stewards with practical skills and resources.

- Provide a foundation for sustainability through adoption guidance and integration into ELIXIR's BFSP roadmap.

Work Package 8 - Creation of a virtual assistant guiding plant researchers in making their datasets FAIR compliant

WP 8	Lead Partner: NL-Utrecht, BE-VIB
	Start month - End month: M25-M36
WP Partnership	
NL-UTRECHT, Auke Damstra, Lead (WP and Activity 4) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 2 and Activity 3)	
BE-VIB, Stijn Dhondt, Lead (WP and Activity 2) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 3 and Activity 4), Rafael Abbeloos, Lead (Activity 2) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
NL-DELFT, Balasubrahmanyam Estamsetty, Lead (Activity 2) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
DE-IPK, Daniel Arend, Lead (Activity 3) , Member (Activity 2 and Activity 4), Manuel Feser, Lead (Activity 3) , Member (Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
DE-FZJU, Sebastian Beier, Member (Activity 1, Activity 2, Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
Total	

Objectives

Background and Rationale

The creation of high-quality, machine-readable metadata is the foundation of the FAIR data principles, yet it remains a significant bottleneck in the research lifecycle. While powerful standards like ISA and MIAPPE provide the necessary structure, their implementation often relies on complex forms and templates that researchers can find cumbersome and time-consuming to complete. This friction leads to incomplete, inconsistent, or missing metadata, which severely limits the long-term value and reusability of valuable scientific datasets, particularly in complex fields like plant phenotyping where data is often heterogeneous, combining images, sensor data, and descriptive text. Consider a researcher with a typical phenotyping experiment: hundreds of drone images, sensor data in CSV files, and crucial observations recorded in a digital lab notebook. Manually transcribing, structuring, and mapping this information to a MIAPPE-compliant format is a multi-day task that is both error-prone and a significant diversion from primary research. The result is often a 'metadata debt' that is either paid

at a high cost of time and effort or, more commonly, left unpaid, rendering the data difficult to reuse by others.

This project is founded on a simple but powerful observation: while many researchers are unfamiliar with the intricacies of metadata standards, all are experts at describing their own research. The MetaBuddy project will lean into this principle by developing a "virtual assistant" that engages researchers in a natural language conversation about their experiment. The assistant will intelligently parse this conversation, identify key metadata components, map them to appropriate ontologies, and structure them according to community standards. In addition to the conversational interface, the application will be able to extract metadata directly from uploaded documents, providing a dual-pronged approach to simplifying data annotation. By capturing not only the required technical metadata but also "soft" metadata — such as the intended applications of the data or subjective assessments of its quality — MetaBuddy will create a richer, more contextualised record of the research process.

Alignment with ELIXIR's Strategic Goals

The MetaBuddy project is directly aligned with the core objectives of the ELIXIR 2024-28 Scientific Programme and the Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP) Priority Area, particularly its focus on FAIR data, standards, and training.

- FAIR Data and Standards: Our project directly tackles the primary barrier to FAIR data — the difficulty of creating it. By generating standard-compliant ISA-JSON and RO-Crate outputs from natural language, MetaBuddy will dramatically increase the volume of high-quality, interoperable, and reusable data. This directly supports the BFSP's objective to "support the development and adoption of community standards and research data management best practices."
- Training and Usability: The conversational interface serves as a form of implicit training. It guides researchers to provide the necessary information without requiring them to become experts in the underlying data models. This user-centric approach addresses the human factors that are often overlooked in data management, making FAIR principles accessible to a broader range of scientists and supporting the BFSP's training and knowledge exchange objectives.
- Federation and Analysis: By ensuring that datasets are born FAIR with rich metadata, MetaBuddy will enhance their suitability for inclusion in federated data ecosystems and their readiness for complex co-analysis. This contributes to the BFSP's goals of strengthening interactions between biodata resources and promoting reliable, reproducible data analyses.

MetaBuddy is envisioned as a novel service that complements, rather than replaces, existing ELIXIR tools. By integrating with the ISA Wizard

(<https://github.com/IPK-BIT/isa-wizard>), a user-friendly application for creating FAIR- and ISA-compliant metadata for results of life science experiments, it will enhance a community resource while also providing a new, standalone entry point for FAIR data creation.

Overall Objectives

Derived from the strategic context above, the MetaBuddy project will work towards these four primary objectives:

1. Develop a Conversational AI Service: To design and build a robust, scalable AI service capable of extracting and structuring metadata from natural language conversations and unstructured documents.
2. Deploy User-Centric Applications: To deliver the AI service's capabilities to researchers through two distinct, practical applications: a new standalone web application ("MetaBuddy") and a direct integration into the existing ISA Wizard.
3. Promote FAIR Standards Adoption: To facilitate the creation of rich, standards-compliant metadata by outputting interoperable formats, including ISA-JSON and RO-Crate, directly from user input.
4. Disseminate and Foster Community Adoption: To deliver the entire project as an open-source tool, host the web application as a sustainable service, and engage with the community to ensure its widespread use and future development.

Description of work

The project is structured into three interconnected activities, progressing from core technology development to interface definition and final application deployment.

Activity 1: Concept and Development of AI Services (2 PMs) (*Lead: Balasubrahmanyam Estamsetty (NL); Members: Stijn Dhondt, Rafael Abbeloos (BE), Auke Damstra (NL), Sebastian Beier (DE). M25-M36*).

- design architecture & set-up infrastructure (MS1)
- select LLM model (OpenAI, Google, Ollama, etc) & select datasets for RAG
- agentic approach ([MCP](#))
- set-up and data integration of AI service (D1)

Activity 1 focuses on designing and building the core AI engine that powers the metadata extraction. The work involves designing the overall system architecture, selecting the current optimal Large Language Model (LLM) from options like OpenAI, Google, or open-source alternatives via Ollama, and establishing the necessary cloud infrastructure. The AI engine will be designed so that it can use different LLM's, as technology advances rapidly and LLM preference might change in the future. A key

technical aspect will be the development of an agentic pipeline, guided by principles from the Model Context Protocol (MCP). This pipeline will consist of several collaborating AI agents: a 'Listener Agent' to manage the conversational flow and capture user input; an 'Extraction Agent' to parse uploaded documents and identify potential metadata fields; an 'Ontology Agent' to map identified terms (e.g., 'wheat', 'leaf senescence') to established ontologies like the Crop Ontology, EDAM, or FOODON; and a 'Formatter Agent' to assemble the validated information into the final, standard-compliant ISA-JSON or RO-Crate structure. This activity culminates in the setup and initial data integration of the AI service, forming the intelligent backend for the entire system.

Activity 2: API and Interface Specifications (1.5 PMs) *(Lead: Stijn Dhondt, Rafael Abbeloos (BE); Members: Daniel Arend, Manuel Feser, Sebastian Beier (DE), Auke Damstra, Balasubrahmanyam Estamsetty (NL). M25-M36).*

- define API specification for AI Service for the use cases of Activity 3 (MS2)
 - define parameters and return format
- set-up REST interface with required API endpoints (D2)

With the core AI service established, Activity 2 will define how it communicates with other applications. The central task is to create a detailed API specification that outlines how the service will be used by the two use cases defined in Activity 3. This includes defining the necessary parameters, request formats, and the structure of the returned metadata. Following the specification, a robust REST interface with the required API endpoints will be implemented.

Activity 3: Application Deployment and Integration (5 PMs) *(Lead: Daniel Arend, Manuel Feser (DE); Members: Balasubrahmanyam Estamsetty, Auke Damstra (NL), Stijn Dhondt, Rafael Abbeloos (BE), Sebastian Beier (DE). M25-M36).*

- implement integration of the AI service in ISA Wizard (D3)
- implement MetaBuddy web application using the AI service (D4)

Activity 3 leverages the API developed in Activity 2 to deliver two practical, user-facing applications. The first use case involves the direct integration of the AI service into the existing ISA Wizard tool. This will be implemented as a new 'MetaBuddy' component accessible within the ISA Wizard interface. When activated, it will open a conversational panel where users can describe a study, assay, or sample. The extracted metadata will then be used to pre-populate the relevant fields in the active ISA JSON, turning a manual entry task into a guided conversation. The second use case is the development of "MetaBuddy," a standalone web application that provides a dedicated conversational interface for researchers to annotate their experiments and datasets. The user flow will allow for the uploading of documents (e.g., protocols, material lists) which the assistant will use as context for the subsequent conversation, streamlining the annotation

process even further. The web application enables users to start a session at the beginning of their research and come back later to add metadata. Both implementations will serve as powerful demonstrations of the AI service's utility and flexibility.

Activity 4: Connecting the Dots - Data Gathering (in kind) *(Lead: Auke Damstra (NL); Members: Stijn Dhondt, Rafael Abbeloos (BE), Balasubrahmanyam Estamsetty (NL), Sebastian Beier, Daniel Arend, Manuel Feser (DE). M25-M36).*

- create documentation and training material on Metabuddy usage and organize a workshop presenting a demo of both use cases (D5)

Activity 4 focusses on getting the word out on this new tool, receiving feedback and reaching out to the Plant Science community, specifically the ELIXIR community. We plan to do this at 3 timepoints:

- Concept demonstration in April (at BFSP event in Amsterdam)
- Prototype demo in June (at All-hands meeting in Lyon)
- A workshop will be organized to showcase the new tool. We aim to organize this linked to a conference, an ELIXIR BioHackathon or community meeting, with the possibility to have it as a webinar as a fallback option.

Feedback will be collected during these events and used to steer development of the app. Outcomes of the project and outreach activities will be also shared with the European plant phenotyping community via interaction with the EMPHASIS Coordination Office.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D8.1 (Activity 1)	Set-up and data integration of AI service	NL-Delft	M29
D8.2 (Activity 2)	Set-up REST interface with required API endpoints	BE-VIB	M32
D8.3 (Activity 3)	Implement integration of the AI service in ISA Wizard	DE-IPK	M34
D8.4 (Activity 3)	Implement MetaBuddy web application using the AI service	DE-IPK	M35
D8.5 (Activity 4)	Create documentation and training material and organize a workshop presenting a demo of both use cases	NL-Utrecht/UU	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month

M8.1 (Activity 1)	Design architecture & set-up infrastructure	NL-Delft	M27
M8.2 (Activity 2)	Define API specification for AI Service for the use cases of Activity 3	BE-VIB	M30

Outcomes and impact

The MetaBuddy project is designed to deliver a transformative service that addresses a fundamental challenge in data management: the user-experience gap in creating FAIR metadata. By shifting the paradigm from manual form-filling to intuitive conversation, we will significantly lower the barrier to high-quality data annotation, generating immediate and lasting value for ELIXIR and the wider research community.

Expected Outcomes

- The project will deliver a suite of tangible, open-source assets:
- A Conversational AI Service: A robust, containerised AI service capable of extracting structured metadata from natural language and unstructured documents. The service will be accessible via a well-documented REST API, allowing for its integration into diverse applications.
- Ready-to-Use Applications: Two fully functional applications will be delivered to showcase the service's utility: the standalone MetaBuddy web application and a direct integration module for the ISA Wizard, enhancing a trusted community tool with conversational capabilities.
- FAIR-by-Design Outputs: The service will generate standards-compliant metadata files, including ISA-JSON for experimental descriptions and RO-Crate packages, ensuring that the outputs are immediately interoperable and ready for deposition in public repositories, such as a FAIRDOM-SEEK node. Support for the ARC RO-crate format will be taken into consideration as it would facilitate making the data available in a BrAPI instance.

Long-Term Value and Impact

- The long-term impact of MetaBuddy lies in its support for innovation, integration, and sustainability within the ELIXIR ecosystem. Innovation and Uptake: By focusing on human-centric design, MetaBuddy introduces a novel approach to a persistent problem. This innovation in user experience is key to driving the voluntary uptake and adoption of FAIR data practices. The intuitive nature of the tool will empower researchers who are not data management experts to produce high-quality metadata, directly benefiting ELIXIR Communities like Plant Sciences, Food & Nutrition, and Marine Metagenomics.

- Integration and Benefit to ELIXIR Services: The project directly integrates with and enhances the ELIXIR-recommended ISA-tools suite (<https://isa-tools.org/index.html>). By making it easier to create rich ISA-JSON, MetaBuddy will improve the quality and completeness of data submitted to ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases, reducing the curation burden and increasing the value of these services for everyone.
- The standardized metadata collection will particularly benefit the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community and support interactions with EMPHASIS's distributed phenotyping facilities by ensuring consistent data quality across the network.
- Sustainability and Reuse: Our commitment to sustainability is twofold. First, the entire project will be developed as open-source software and made available on GitHub, allowing for community contributions and reuse. Second, we aim to host the MetaBuddy web application as a sustainable service beyond the project's lifetime, providing a persistent, low-maintenance tool for the community. This ensures the project's outputs will continue to facilitate FAIR data creation long after the initial funding period.

Work Package 9 - FAIRferm: FAIRifying Microbiome–Metabolome Time-Series Data from Food Fermentation Processes

WP 9	Lead Partner: <i>GR-AUTH, UK-Quadram</i>
	Start month - End month: M25-M36
WP Partnership	
GR-AUTH, Fani Mantzouridou, Lead (WP, Activity 2 and Activity 4) , Member (Activity 2 and Activity 3)	
UK-Quadram, Maria Traka, Lead (WP, Activity 1 and Activity 2) , Member (Activity 4)	
IT-CNR, Bachir Balech, Lead (Activity 1) , Member (Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
PT-BioData, Teresa Nogueira, Lead (Activity 3) , Member (Activity 4)	
EMBL-EBI, Robert Finn, Member (Activity 1, Activity 2 and Activity 4), Thomas Payne, Member (Activity 1, Activity 2 and Activity 4), Juan Antonio Vizcaino, Member (Activity 4)	
NL-Leiden, Jildau Bouwman, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 4)	
NL-Wageningen, Jasper Koehorst, Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
GR-FORTH, Maria Klapa, Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
GR-NKUA, Zoi Litou, Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
CH-SIB, Cornelia Bär, Member (Activity 2 and Activity 4), Rémy Bruggman, Member (Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
Total	

Objectives

Plant-based fermented foods (FF) are critical for sustainable food security, yet their optimization faces data science challenges identified in ELIXIR's BFSP strategy: fragmented data mobilization, siloed repositories limiting interoperability, and inadequate tools for integrated analysis. The management of plant-based food fermentation, for which pre-selected starter strains remain uncommon even for large-scale production, still relies heavily on empirical knowledge, as intricate dynamics of microbial communities and metabolic networks producing safe, nutritious products are not fully understood. However, growing availability of omics data generated during production of various plant-based FF provides an opportunity to develop understanding of microbial relationships that shape fermentation processes. With this project we aim

to build an integrative FAIR framework for omics data to evaluate microbial community dynamics during fermentation, accelerating innovation in FF.

Although such datasets exist and provide information, they are not yet fully FAIRified. They require sophisticated approaches for analysis efforts that remain fragmented, necessitating advancements in data science, enhanced ontologies, robust databases, improved harmonization, and development of algorithms and tools for data sharing and dissemination, which is challenging to achieve in microbial ecology and fermentation studies.

Within ELIXIR, resources such as Phenotype Database, MGnify and MetaboLights provide solutions for sharing and integrating phenotypic, microbiome and metabolomics data, respectively. Within this project, Food & Nutrition Community, together with the Microbiome and Metabolomics Communities, will extend these frameworks to include time-series datasets—particularly multi-omics data generated at distinct stages of plant-based FF production. Challenges arise in aligning time-series omics data through environmental or process metadata, crucial for understanding factors driving microbial community changes. Integrating these datasets with broader metabolomics and microbiome research platforms requires improved standardizing tools and interoperability practices (via ELIXIR Interoperability, Data, and Tools Platform). Developing such infrastructure would enable insights into temporal dynamics of microbial communities and their metabolic outputs, enhancing dataset availability and usability within ELIXIR and beyond.

Within ELIXIR, the Nutritional Phenotype Database (dbNP) is an ontology-driven platform for storing and managing diverse biological studies. It supports a broad range of experimental designs through customizable templates, enabling researchers to tailor data capture according to study-specific requirements while maintaining consistency across datasets. Within this project, the Food & Nutrition Community will extend this framework to include time-series datasets, especially multi-omics data generated at distinct stages of fermentation. Aligning time-series omics data with environmental or process metadata remains crucial for understanding factors driving microbial community changes. The use of dbNP platform as a central integration framework for these datasets, alongside data from broader metabolomics and microbiome platforms (such as MGnify and MetaboLights), will require implementation of advanced standardization tools and robust interoperability practices to support linking datasets across resources. These capabilities are supported through ELIXIR Interoperability, Data, and Tools Platforms, but further development and alignment will be essential to enable seamless data integration and reuse. Such approach enables implementation of key aspects towards microbial community dynamics modeling as it aligns with FAIR data principles ensuring sustainability and integration of outcomes.

Description of work

Activity 1: Gap Analysis and Requirements Definition (2 PMs).

The primary objective of Activity 1 is to identify gaps and deficiencies in existing data repositories and brokering services and standards required to advance fermentation process monitoring and to enable a comprehensive investigation of microbiota and metabolite dynamics, including their integrated correlations, thereby supporting the optimized production of FF. It aims to establish a comprehensive understanding of the requirements for improving data collection and selection, metadata annotation, and standardization practices in the field. The focus is on enabling the successful integration of time-series datasets capturing targeted 16S rRNA gene and ITS amplicon sequencing, shotgun metagenomic and GC-MS metabolomics time-series datasets during the fermentation process into existing omics data resources, particularly within the ELIXIR ecosystem.

Task 1. Review of Existing Resources (*Lead: Bachir Balech (FR); Members: Maria Traka (UK), Robert Finn, Thomas Payne (EMBL-EBI), Jildau Bouwman (NL) . M25-M36*).

A thorough review will be conducted to map and evaluate existing databases and standards relevant to FF research. This will include key resources from the dbNP, MGnify and MetaboLights as well as BioSamples for sample linkage. The review will also cover relevant data standards, including data formats that define how files are structured and metadata standards that ensure consistent, interoperable data descriptions across studies. The aim is to assess the usability, coverage, and limitations of these resources in supporting time-series microbiome and metabolome data generated from dynamic fermentation processes (D1).

Task 2. Challenges in Interoperability and Data Sustainability (*Lead: Maria Traka (UK); Members: Bachir Balech (FR), Robert Finn, Thomas Payne (EMBL-EBI), Jildau Bouwman (NL). M25-M36*).

This task will identify major obstacles to database and tool interoperability, focusing on differences in metadata standards and the maintenance of long-term data accessibility and usability. It will highlight gaps in

current databases and standards for sequencing-based and GC-MS metabolomics time-series datasets from fermentation studies, and provide recommendations for extending ELIXIR tools, ontologies, and pipelines. It will also offer guidelines to harmonize FF data management with broader microbiome and metabolome research initiatives (MS1).

Activity 2: Relevant Data Collection, Curation & Training (3 PMs).

In this work package, time-series datasets derived from targeted 16S, ITS amplicon sequencing and/or shotgun metagenomics (i.e. one or more approaches), and GC-MS metabolomics from relevant studies on plant-based FF systems, particularly during fermentation processes, will be prepared and deposited in ELIXIR databases. As part of this effort, technical support will be provided to community members for the submission of data to MGnify and MetaboLights, ensuring that standardized practices and SOPs are directly applied to key data repositories. Also, community members will be trained in standardized data practices that will serve as the foundation for plant-based applications to use the systems).

Task 1. Technical Support for Repository Submissions (*Lead: Fani Mantzouridou (GR); Members: Jekaterina Kazantseva (TFTAK), Robert Finn, Thomas Payne (EMBL-EBI), Zoi I. Litou (GR), Maria Traka (UK), Bachir Balech (FR). M25-M36*)

This activity will provide technical support and training for the deposition of curated datasets into key repositories. EMBL-EBI will lead the efforts for submissions to MGnify (sequencing-derived datasets) and MetaboLights (GC-MS metabolomic datasets). Partners will ensure that the datasets comply with the repository's requirements. Training materials will leverage TeSS resources and be continuously updated with workflow improvements from WP3 to remain aligned with best practices via ELIXIR Training SPLASH. This integrated support will secure the visibility, reusability, and long-term interoperability of the datasets (MS2, MS3, D2)

Task 2. Metadata Standards and Dataset Preparation (*Lead: Maria Traka (UK); Members: Fani Mantzouridou (GR), Jekaterina Kazantseva (TFTAK), Bachir Balech (FR), Robert Finn, Thomas Payne (EMBL-EBI), Cornelia Bär, Rémy Bruggman (CH). M25-M36*)

This activity will focus on the implementation of metadata standards for food fermentation experiments, with emphasis on time-series data. Using plant-based fermentation datasets (phenotype, sequencing-derived, and GC-MS), partners will curate datasets that employ controlled vocabularies and identifiers within the dbNP resource. The feasibility for BioSamplesID or other solutions to facilitate cross-linking will be explored. The resulting workflows will ensure dataset reuse, interoperability, and alignment with analysis pipelines in WP3. Together with Activity 3, efforts will lead to the development of a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)/toolset to guarantee optimal FAIR data practices in food fermentation research. (D3)

Activity 3: Microbiome & Metabolomics Workflow and Pipeline/Standards Development & Implementation (3 PMs) (*Lead: Teresa Nogueira (PT); Members: Maria Klapa, Fani Mantzouridou (GR), Jekaterina Kazantseva (TFTAK), Jasper Koehorst (NL) . M25-M36*).

To identify and integrate bioinformatics tools and develop reproducible, FAIR-compliant workflows for analysing plant-associated microbial communities and their metabolic outputs during fermentation, enabling comprehensive time-series analysis and supporting broad use within the fermented food research community.

Task 1. Identification and Integration of Bioinformatics Tools and Development of FAIR Reproducible Workflows

This task focuses on identifying, integrating, and implementing robust bioinformatics tools and reproducible workflows to analyse the dynamics of plant-associated microbial communities and their metabolic outputs during fermentation. Tools will be selected from the bio.tools platform (<https://bio.tools>) and combined with biostatistics and machine learning approaches to enable comprehensive analysis of temporal variations in fermentation samples. Based on these tools, reproducible workflows will be developed for sequencing-based omics and GC-MS metabolomics, adhering to FAIR principles to ensure accessibility, transparency, and reusability. The workflows will be integrated into platforms such as ELIXIR Toolbox and Galaxy, and aligned with recipes from the FAIR Cookbook (<https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/>), providing valuable resources for the broader fermented food research community. Adjustments will be made as needed, and input will be provided for training materials within the ELIXIR Training Platform (D4).

Activity 4: Community engagement and sustainability of FAIR fermented foods datasets (2 PMs) (*Lead: Fani Mantzouridou (GR); Members: Maria Traka (UK), Maria Klapa, Zoi I. Litou (GR), Jildau Bouwman (NL), Juan Antonio Vizcaino, Robert Finn, Thomas Payne (EMBL-EBI), Teresa Nogueira (PT), Bachir Balech (IT), Cornelia Bär, Rémy Bruggman (CH), Jasper Koehorst (NL). M25-M36).*

Activity 4 aims to accelerate adoption of FAIR principles within the Food & Nutrition Community, identifying barriers to barriers to FAIR data adoption and co-developing recommendations for comprehensive metadata capture during data production.

Task 1. Hackathon and Community Engagement

A hackathon will be organized to engage different stakeholders (data owners, tool developers, resource managers and software engineers). The goal will be to disseminate findings, further engage with the community in FAIR principles (e.g. PIMENTO & DOMINO fermented food consortia), and provide recommendations for future database development, validate proposals, and ensure relevance and feasibility of proposed standards (D5).

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D9.1 (Activity 1)	Gap analysis report on time-series fermentation monitoring data in ELIXIR repositories and guidelines for standardisation	IT-CNR	M27
D9.2 (Activity 2)	FAIR submission of time-series sequencing-derived and GC-MS datasets from food fermentation	GR-AUTH	M31
D9.3 (Activity 2)	Development of SOP for optimal time-series food fermentation data FAIRNESS	UK-QIB	M32
D9.4 (Activity 2)	FAIR-compliant workflows and bioinformatics pipelines for time-series analysis of microbiome and metabolomics data in plant-based food fermentation	PT-BioData	M34
D9.5 (Activity 2)	Report from hackathon	GR-AUTH	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M9.1 (Activity 1)	Develop a set of minimal metadata required for food fermentation datasets	UK-QIB	M28
M9.2 (Activity 2)	Technical support to the submission of data to MGnify	EMBL-EBI	M29
M9.3 (Activity 3)	Technical support to the submission of data to MetaboLights	EMBL-EBI	M29

Outcomes and impact

This project directly tackles the three key technical challenges outlined in the BFSP strategy: (1) Data brokering services through our SOP development and technical support for repository submissions, (2) Resource interoperability via BioSamples ID linking and metadata harmonization across MGnify, MetaboLights, and dbNP, and (3) Co-analysis tools through our FAIR-compliant temporal analysis pipelines.

We aim to deliver:

- The project will deliver key technical outputs to support FAIR data practices and systems-level analysis in food fermentation research.
- A comprehensive analysis to inform harmonized metadata standards for time-series omics (metataxonomi, metagenomic, metabolomic) datasets.
- Well-annotated, FAIRified datasets from selected plant-based fermentation studies to be submitted to ENA/MGnify and MetaboLights and linked via

BioSamples IDs in Nutritional Phenotype Database (dbNP), a FAIR-compliant community resource.

- Reproducible, FAIR-compliant pipelines for time-series analysis of microbiome and metabolome data developed and integrated into the ELIXIR Toolbox.
- Modular training resources to support community adoption, focusing on standardized data submission and curation using plant-based systems.
- Finally, the project will create an integrated, cross-platform resource via dbNP, offering centralized access to curated and linked datasets to enable dynamic analyses across domains. These outputs will enhance interoperability, data reuse, and capacity building within the ELIXIR ecosystem.
- The proposed work will be supported by the collaboration between researchers involved in EU-funded fermented food projects, including PIMENTO Cost Action (PIMENTO – COST ACTION CA20128 – Promoting Innovation of ferMENTEd fOods) and DOMINO (<https://www.domino-euproject.eu/>). Notably, [TETAK](#) provides in-kind contributions as a DOMINO Horizon Europe member, showcasing strong involvement and added value from partners (data owners) outside the ELIXIR network. The findings will be communicated back to PIMENTO and DOMINO so that the extended fermented food community benefits. In addition, this will be a use case for other communities within ELIXIR to benefit from.
- These deliverables directly advance BFSP priorities by demonstrating auto-validating brokering solutions, achieving seamless connections between heterogeneous data infrastructures, and enabling intuitive interfaces for complex temporal analyses - fulfilling the vision of connected FAIR data routinely informing food security research.
- The integrated framework developed will serve as a replicable model for other time-series multi-omics applications within BFSP domains, particularly in biodiversity monitoring and pathogen surveillance, where temporal dynamics are equally critical. By demonstrating successful metadata harmonization across heterogeneous platforms, this project establishes technical precedents for connecting disparate data types - a core challenge identified in the BFSP strategy. The approach will directly inform future ELIXIR initiatives requiring cross-domain data integration under the One Health framework.

Work Package 10 - KYBELE: Knowledge Yield from Biodiversity Literature through Large Language Model (LLM) Extraction

WP 10	Lead Partner: <i>GR-HCMR, CH-SIB</i>
	Start month - End month: M25-M36
WP Partnership	
GR-HCMR, Stelios Ninidakis, Lead (WP, Activity 3 and Activity 5) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 2 and Activity 5), Dimitra Mavraki, Lead (Activity 4) , Member (Activity 1 and Activity 3), Savvas Paragkamian, Lead (Activity 4) , Member (Activity 1 and Activity 3)	
CH-SIB, Patrick Ruch, Lead (WP, Activity 2 and Activity 5) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 3 and Activity 4), Luc Mottin, Member (Activity 1, Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
IT-Naples, Matteo Montagna, Lead (Activity 1) , Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
IT-CNR, Bachir Balech, Lead (Activity 1) , Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
LifeWatch ERIC, Christos Arvanitidis	
Total	

Objectives

The initial goal of KYBELE is to build an AI-powered, FAIR-compliant, and user-friendly system for extracting, integrating, and exploring biodiversity knowledge, by connecting genomic resources with ecological and taxonomic information. The approach is driven by the societal need for rapid biodiversity monitoring tools that also capture functional diversity and associated ecosystem services, enabling better assessment of human impacts. As a demonstrator, KYBELE will focus on a selected target group; once the pipeline is established and integrated into the ELIXIR portfolio, it can be expanded to other taxonomic groups and ultimately serve as a reference standard for EU-based biodiversity monitoring.

The project will pursue four main objectives:

- **Data harvesting and FAIRification:** Focusing on the target organism groups, only taxa listed in Fauna Europaea for which reference DNA sequences are available in [BOLD](#) will be considered. For these taxa, structured catalogues of species names, habitats, and ecological traits will be compiled from existing, more accurate resources, and annotate [BiodiversityPMC](#) with domain-specific vocabularies, ensuring FAIR compliance.
- **AI-driven literature exploration:** Develop and fine-tune generative language models (using LoRA and distillation) for retrieval-augmented question answering

on biodiversity literature, while maintaining Data provenance and sovereignty, an approach that mainstream LLMs are not implementing.

- Deployment and integration: Operationalise the system as a containerised biodiversity chatbox, deployed jointly within ELIXIR and LifeWatch ERIC, ensuring accessibility, interoperability, and long-term sustainability.
- Dissemination and training: Create and provide a user guideline, training material, and participating in community events (e.g. ELIXIR BioHackathon, BEES LifeWatch Conference) to ensure visibility, and knowledge/technological transfer.

These objectives are directly aligned to the ELIXIR 2024–28 Scientific Programme and the Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP) Priority Area, by advancing FAIR biodiversity data integration, linking biodiversity research domains (molecular and conventional), enabling AI-based services for life sciences, and fostering collaboration between ELIXIR Nodes and European Research Infrastructures.

Description of work

Activity 1: Data harvesting, synthesis and FAIRification [M01-M05,M08,M10] (3.5 PMs) (Lead: Matteo Montagna, Bachir Balech (IT); Members: Stelios Ninidakis, Dimitra Mavraki, Savvas Paragkamanian (GR), Patrick Ruch, Luc Mottin (CH), Christos Arvanitidis (LifeWatch ERIC) all. M25-M30/M33/M34).

This activity establishes the project's foundation by collecting species and trait data from BOLD (a repository which already provides COI sequences for the target species group) and other public resources, creating controlled vocabularies for habitats and trophic guilds, and annotating BiodiversityPMC with domain-specific terms. Semi-automated curation and FAIRification will ensure taxonomic accuracy, interoperability, and long-term reusability. The outcome will be a curated, FAIR-aligned catalogue of species, traits, and habitats that underpins all subsequent KYBELE activities.

Task 1.1. This task will define a standardised list of species from Fauna Europaea with available COI sequences in BOLD (target groups: soil invertebrates essential for soil structure and health such as Collembola and Oligochaeta), together with a thesaurus of habitats and ecological traits. It will include: (a) retrieval of species names, COI DNA barcode sequence and relative metadata from BOLD, (b) development of a controlled vocabulary of habitat types, and (c) creation of a trophic guild catalogue, linking species to key ecological traits such as feeding preferences, substrate associations, and behavioural or morphological characteristics.

Task 1.2. Annotate BiodiversityPMC with domain-specific vocabularies. New annotations will be generated in BiodiversityPMC using the vocabularies identified in T1.1 to extend current biodiversity-related terminologies (e.g., Open Tree of Life, NCBI Taxonomy,

ENVO, Agrovoc). An evaluation of the annotations' accuracy will be performed on a limited sample of taxonomic descriptions (n=50).

Task 1.3. Bootstrap a large positive sample of taxonomic treatments (N>100'000 instances).

Task 1.4. Semi-manual curation & FAIRification: Development of ad hoc scripts to verify taxon names in different taxonomy backbones (i.e. NCBI, Catalogue of Life, Synospecies, etc.), metadata and ecological traits and to ensure FAIR data compliance.

Activity 2: Interactive literature exploration (2 PMs) (*Lead: Patrick Ruch, Luc Mottin (CH); Members: Stelios Ninidakis (GR). M28-M30*).

A large language model (e.g., Llama, T5, BERT large) will be deployed to prompt the Biodiversity PMC APIs in order to perform Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) and Question-Answering (QA). The input of the language model will be both the search and the factoid Question-Answering APIs of BiodiversityPMC, while natural language outputs will be based on JSON, outputs will highlight relevant JATS/BioC narrative in the body in the reference publications. The final Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) augmented model (Hu et al., 2021) & fine-tuning will be evaluated against SOTA LLM and embedded to expand existing APIs (based on <https://sibils.org/api/biodiversitypmc/fetch/>). LifeWatch ERIC granted access to a powerful GPU based virtual machine on their premises, which would guarantee the technical capabilities for the development of such a model. If more computational needs arise, we would also apply for short-term access to cloud services of ELIXIR-GR or ELIXIR-IT (e.g. HYPATIA cloud system).

Task 2.1. Parameter-efficient techniques such as Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) and benchmark-based fine-tuning will be used to reduce the number of trainable parameters while retaining core capabilities by inserting and training small adapter matrices.

Task 2.2. Knowledge distillation methods will be applied to reduce the computational footprint of the LoRA-augmented models while retaining high accuracy in QA tasks. The compact models will then be prepared for evaluation and deployment (see Activity 3).

Activity 3: Refinement and deployment (1.5 PMs) (*Lead: Stelios Ninidakis (GR); Members: Matteo Montagna, Bachir Balech (IT), Dimitra Mavraki, Savvas Paragkamian (GR), Patrick Ruch, Luc Mottin (CH), Christos Arvanitidis (LifeWatch ERIC) all. M31-M33*).

The goal of this activity is to evaluate, refine, and operationalize the KYBELE application, ensuring its integration into biodiversity research infrastructures and its usability by end-users. Building on the results of

Activity 2, the current activity will focus on performance validation, iterative improvement, and deployment of a demonstrator in the LifeWatch ERIC Catalogue.

Task 3.1. Evaluation and benchmarking of the model - Testing of the model and demonstrator from Activity 2 will be performed against the datasets produced in Activity 1. The evaluation criteria will be: entity recognition accuracy, relevance of generated answers, computational efficiency, and usability. We will also collect feedback by biodiversity researchers for real-world testing to refine prompts, LoRA parameters, and inference efficiency. Domain vocabularies from Activity 1 will be further integrated. Optimized and reproducible models will be re-tested for stability. Structured feedback will be collected to guide the last refinements before release.

Task 3.2. Containerize and deploy as a service (ELIXIR & LifeWatch ERIC) - Final version deployment as a public service, with online access. This will involve containerization (Docker/Singularity), and user access management for sustainability. The source code and the Docker recipe will be available on the dedicated projects' repository on [GitHub](#), and indexed on [Bio.Tools](#). The container will be publicly available on [Docker Hub](#) and [BioContainers](#).

Activity 4: Connecting the Dots - Data Gathering (2.25 PMs) (*Lead: Dimitra Mavraki, Savvas Paragkamian (GR); Members: Stelios Ninidakis (GR), Matteo Montagna, Bachir Balech (IT), Patrick Ruch, Luc Mottin (CH), Christos Arvanitidis (LifeWatch ERIC) all.* M30-M31/M35-M36).

The objectives of this activity are a) to disseminate knowledge and raise awareness among young researchers and the general public regarding biodiversity research domain and related in-depth data, as well as b) to expand expertise and adoption of KYBELE tools and outputs through targeted training activities. This activity is essential for transforming project results into community benefits: dissemination at major events will position KYBELE within the European biodiversity research landscape, while structured training will ensure that researchers can effectively use the tools, vocabularies, and services developed. By combining FAIR-aligned documentation and training, Activity 4 secures the long-term visibility, uptake, and sustainability of the project's achievements.

Task 4.1. Participation in scientific community events: The [BEeS LifeWatch ERIC Conference](#) (June 2026, M06) and the [ELIXIR All Hands meeting](#) (June 2026, M06) offer an early opportunity to present the preliminary outcomes of Activities 1 and 2 to the biodiversity research community, thereby increasing the visibility of the project. Moreover, the KYBELE project team aims to apply for participation in the [ELIXIR BioHackathon](#) (November 2026, M10), which will provide not only an opportunity to present and communicate KYBELE to ELIXIR members and participants but also a

valuable setting for the project team to meet, collaborate, and address challenges arising from Activity 3.

Task 4.2. Documentation based on FAIR principles & Training material: All project outputs and data will be documented in line with the FAIR principles to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and long-term usability. This will include clear README files, metadata and data management documentation, complemented by technical and user-oriented presentations/tutorials for both internal and external dissemination. In particular, for training purposes, well-structured presentations will be uploaded to the [TeSS](#) platform, introducing KYBELE to interested users through training materials and/or interactive tutorials.

Activity 5: Project Management and Coordination (1.25 PMs) (Lead: *Stelios Ninidakis (GR), Patrick Ruch (CH)*. M25-M36).

Project management runs across all activities to ensure smooth implementation of KYBELE. It covers coordination, financial administration, and risk management, while fostering transparent communication among partners, ELIXIR, and LifeWatch ERIC.

Task 5.1. Financial and Risk management: Oversee budget execution, financial reporting, PM distribution, compliance with ELIXIR commissioned services requirements, identify risks and track mitigation actions.

Task 5.2. Scientific and technical coordination: Monitor milestones and deliverables across activities, ensuring alignment with the project's objectives.

Task 5.3. Communication and Organization: Facilitate and organize the internal communication (e.g. monthly calls, collaborative platforms).

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D10.1 (Activity 1)	A structured, curated and FAIR catalogue including: taxonomic names of the selected species, standardized trophic guilds and their defining ecological traits, and habitat typologies	IT-UNINA	M34
D10.2 (Activity 2)	A fine-tuned LLM to be deposited on HuggingFace/Zenodo	CH-SIB	M29
D10.3 (Activity 2)	A report describing the model evaluation results based on a curated sample of taxonomic treatment (N>100 instances) and the actions to optimize the entire system	GR-HCMR	M32
D10.4 (Activity 4)	A report summarising the key outcomes of the activity actions, the feedback received, and possible follow-up project steps.	GR-HCMR	M36

Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M10.1 (Activity 1)	All collections of BiodiversityPMC are annotated	IT-CNR	M29
M10.2 (Activity 1)	Taxonomic names, metadata and ecological traits semi-manual curation is completed	IT-CNR	M32
M10.3 (Activity 2)	An agent based demonstrator to interact with the literature	CH-SIB	M30
M10.4 (Activity 3)	Application is publicly available by end-users as an online service.	GR-HCMR	M33
M10.5 (Activity 4)	All outcomes are published (README file and user manuals on GitHub, presentations and training material on TeSS).	GR-HCMR	M36

Outcomes and impact

- KYBELE will deliver concrete outputs that enrich the biodiversity research ecosystem, published on several ELIXIR services and platforms:
- A structured catalogue of European springtails and earthworms, trophic guilds, and habitat typologies, curated and harmonised according to FAIR data principles.
- Annotated BiodiversityPMC collections with domain-specific vocabularies, enabling more precise retrieval and knowledge extraction.
- An AI-enhanced literature exploration tool able to enrich and link biodiversity research domains (molecular and conventional), fine-tuned through LoRA and distillation, openly deposited on HuggingFace/Zenodo.
- A containerised and interoperable chatbox service, deployed jointly on ELIXIR and LifeWatch ERIC platforms, ensuring accessibility, visibility, sustainability and reuse.
- Comprehensive documentation, training material, and dissemination activities, aligned with FAIR data principles and designed for long-term uptake.

Impact:

The project's impact goes beyond technical innovation (enriching biodiversity data with literature locked data, utilizing LLMs' power), by fostering collaboration and creating lasting value for Europe's biodiversity research community:

- Strengthening collaboration across ELIXIR Nodes: KYBELE combines mature and emerging Nodes, integrating expertise in biodiversity, AI, Data Management and Curation and interoperability, and ensuring balanced geographical, gender and cross-disciplinary contributions.

- Deepening integration of EU Research Infrastructures: Through joint collaboration with LifeWatch ERIC, KYBELE demonstrates how complementary infrastructures can align to create added value. Rather than duplicating existing work, it extends BiodiversityPMC and ELIXIR services, creating synergies across RIs.
- Direct benefits for the scientific community: Biodiversity researchers and taxonomists gain access to structured and literature enhanced datasets, a powerful AI-driven exploration tool, and FAIR-compliant resources that reduce barriers to reuse, accelerate discovery, and improve reproducibility.
- Long-term sustainability and innovation: By embedding its outputs into ELIXIR and LifeWatch ERIC, KYBELE ensures that services remain available, trusted, and community-maintained beyond the project's lifetime, while demonstrating how generative AI can be responsibly integrated into Europe's life science infrastructures.
- Scalability, automation, and standardisation: KYBELE establishes a reusable pipeline that begins with a concrete demonstrator and can be expanded to other taxonomic groups, ultimately serving as a reference standard for EU-wide biodiversity monitoring. At the same time, the system is designed to automatically annotate new publications in BiodiversityPMC, with regularly updated vocabularies ensuring alignment with the latest domain knowledge. This combination of scalability, automation, and periodic refresh makes the resource sustainable, future-proof, and open to further collaborative extensions.

Table of Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverable / Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M1.1	2024 Open Call for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	FR-INRAE	M03
M1.2	Cross-Community workshop on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	CH-SIB	M09
D1.1	Report and Roadmap on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens in ELIXIR 2024-2025	CH-SIB	M13
D2.1	Develop standards for assessment of pan-genome completeness	DE-FZJU	M16
M3.4	Data from MGnify with computational resources used for metagenomics assembly	DE-FREIBURG	M18
D4.1	Generate exemplary datasets as reference RO-Crates	DE-IPK	M18
M5.1	Successfully implemented queries to ENA and GBIF	GR-HCMR	M18
D2.2	Computational pipelines to assess pan-genome data quality and characterise gene-based structural variation within pan-genomes	BE-VIB	M19
D3.1	Workflow available on UseGalaxy Europe and UseGalaxy France servers as well as published on IWC and WorkflowHub.	DE-FREIBURG	M20
M3.1	Prototype and metadata of Galaxy workflow	DE-FREIBURG	M20
D2.3	Prototyping and evaluation of data visualisations to represent pan-genome dynamics	DE-IPK	M20
D4.2	RDMkit pages updated and cross referenced on relevant websites	EMBL-EBI	M20
D2.4	Development of API calls and sharing of bulk-downloads to exchange pan-genome information across different platforms (PLAZA/FRINGE and KnetMiner) for the selected plant species	UK-Rothamsted	M22
D3.5	Blogpost summarising the hackathon outcomes	DE-FREIBURG	M22
M3.5	Hackathon in Freiburg	DE-FREIBURG	M22
M3.2	Recovered MAGs for selection of 3 real-world datasets.	DE-FREIBURG	M24
M5.2	First demo of the Odyssey framework	NO-NMBU	M24
M5.3	Training material prepared and delivered in GitHub	GR-CERTH	M24

D1.2	Report and Roadmap on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens in ELIXIR 2025-2026	FR-INRAE	M25
D2.5	Training materials based on crop-specific use cases deposited at TeSS	PT-ITQB NOVA	M25
D2.6	Online workshop to showcase the developed tools and practical use cases	SI-NIB	M25
D3.3	Tutorial hosted on the Galaxy Training Network and visible on ELIXIR' TeSS	FR-IFB	M25
M6.1	Discussion forum for multiple biodiversity communities to express their shared needs	CH-SIB	M26
M6.2	A FAIRness evaluation of representative entries in ENA, BioSample, and DiSSCo	FR-CNRS	M26
M7.1	Complete interviews with 10 domain experts	NO-UiT	M26
M1.3	2026 Open Call for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	GR-HCMR	M27
D3.2	Assessed MAGs and their quality for the 3 selected real-world datasets	DE-FREIBURG	M27
M5.4	Organise an open community event to demonstrate the new resource and its features getting feedback on the user requirements	NO-NMBU	M27
D7.1	Publish gap analysis report	NO-UiT	M27
M8.1	Design architecture & set-up infrastructure	NL-Delft	M27
D9.1	Gap analysis report on time-series fermentation monitoring data in ELIXIR repositories and guidelines for standardisation	IT-CNR	M27
D3.4	Machine-Learning model registered on DOME registry and implemented to predict needed computational resources of metagenomic assembly tools for given input data and rules integrated into Galaxy Total Perspective Vortex (TPV)	DE-FREIBURG	M28
D7.2	Document collecting and comparing existing metadata models and draft schema design for non-human pathogens.	ES-ISCII	M28
M7.2	Metadata model review completed and first draft schema structure agreed with partner communities	ES-ISCII	M28
M9.1	Develop a set of minimal metadata required for food fermentation datasets	UK-QIB	M28

D5.4	Run a virtual training event	GR-CERTH	M29
D8.1	Set-up and data integration of AI service	NL-Delft	M29
M9.2	Technical support to the submission of data to MGnify	EMBL-EBI	M29
M9.3	Technical support to the submission of data to MetaboLights	EMBL-EBI	M29
D10.2	A fine-tuned LLM to be deposited on HuggingFace/Zenodo	CH-SIB	M29
M10.1	All collections of BiodiversityPMC are annotated	IT-CNR	M29
D1.3	Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research 2027-2028 Work Plan	GR-HCMR	M30
D3.6	Abstract for a talk at a conference submitted	FR-IFB	M30
M3.3	Online workshop	FR-IFB	M30
M3.6	Preprint submitted on BioRxiv	FR-IFB	M30
D4.3	Preprint on plant data FAIRification	DE-FZJU	M30
D4.4	Extension of FAIDARE Indexing (use PLANTdataHUB as use case), extension to other relevant repositories prepared (Dataverse, Zenodo)	FR-INRAE	M30
D4.5	Webinar on guidelines	DE-FZJU	M30
D5.1	Report on the overview of relevant molecular biodiversity data in Greece and Norway	GR-HCMR	M30
D5.2	Back-end (database, schema, etc)	NO-NMBU	M30
D5.3	Front-end (shiny app, GitHub repo)	GR-CERTH	M30
D5.5	Final project report	GR-DUTH	M30
D6.1	Minimal and recommended biodiversity metadata fields	CH-SIB	M30
D7.3	Publish harmonised metadata templates for non-human pathogens, aligned with ontologies and repository requirements.	ES-ISCII	M30
M7.3	Draft templates validated for structure/compatibility with ENA and BioStudies submission pipelines.	ES-ISCII	M30
M8.2	Define API specification for AI Service for the use cases of Activity 3	BE-VIB	M30
M10.3	An agent based demonstrator to interact with the literature	CN-SIB	M30

D6.2	Biodiv FAIR metrics implementation	FR-CNRS	M31
M6.3	Expose Biodiv-FC through the RDMkit ecosystem	UK-UoM	M31
D9.2	FAIR submission of time-series sequencing-derived and GC-MS datasets from food fermentation	GR-AUTH	M31
D8.2	Set-up REST interface with required API endpoints	BE-VIB	M32
D9.3	Development of SOP for optimal time-series food fermentation data FAIRNESS	UK-QIB	M32
D10.3	A report describing the model evaluation results based on a curated sample of taxonomic treatment (N>100 instances) and the actions to optimize the entire system	GR-HCMR	M32
M10.2	Taxonomic names, metadata and ecological traits semi-manual curation is completed	IT-CNR	M32
M1.4	Cross-Community workshop on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	GR-HCMR	M33
D6.3	Biodiv metadata profile (Bioschemas profile + SHACL rules)	UK-UoM	M33
M10.4	Application is publicly available by end-users as an online service.	GR-HCMR	M33
D7.4	Pilot datasets deposited with harmonised metadata	PT-BioDat	M34
D7.5	Short evaluation report documenting lessons learned and proposed improvements	PT-BioDat	M34
M7.4	Harmonised metadata templates tested and validated	PT-BioDat	M34
D8.3	Implement integration of the AI service in ISA Wizard	DE-IPK	M34
D9.4	FAIR-compliant workflows and bioinformatics pipelines for time-series analysis of microbiome and metabolomics data in plant-based food fermentation	PT-BioData	M34
D10.1	A structured, curated and FAIR catalogue including: taxonomic names of the selected species, standardized trophic guilds and their defining ecological traits, and habitat typologies	IT-UNINA	M34
D7.6	Training Materials - Complete set of expert-led presentations, hands-on exercises, and reusable training content for microbial data management, including a module focused on non-human pathogen data.	DE-FZJU	M35

D8.4	Implement MetaBuddy web application using the AI service	DE-IPK	M35
D1.4	Final Report 2024-2026	CH-SIB	M36
D6.4	FAIR-Checker biodiversity plugin	FR-CNRS	M36
M7.5	Training Event - Deliver at least one online interactive training event, including presentations, hands-on exercises, and dedicated pathogen data session.	DE-FZJU	M36
D8.5	Create documentation and training material and organize a workshop presenting a demo of both use cases	NL-Utrecht/UU	M36
D9.5	Report from hackathon	GR-AUTH	M36
D10.4	A report summarising the key outcomes of the activity actions, the feedback received, and possible follow-up project steps.	GR-HCMR	M36
M10.5	All outcomes are published (README file and user manuals on GitHub, presentations and training material on TeSS).	GR-HCMR	M36

Appendix A: Partner information

Partner contact information

Institution	Contact Name
CH-SIB	Rob Waterhouse ORCID
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DE-IPK	Daniel Arend ORCID , Uwe Scholz ORCID , Manuel Feser
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